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Nomenclature

Acronyms

A Event A

B Event B

AEMET Agencia Estatal de Meteorología

ANNs Artificial Neural Networks

API Application Programming Interface

DEM Digital Elevation Model

DSO Distribution System Operator

EMS Energy Management System

ETRS89 European Terrestrial Reference System 1989

GEOVEG Grup de Recerca de Geobotànica i Cartografia de la Vegetació

GIS Geographical Information System

GLI Green Leaf Index

ICGC Institut Cartogràfic i Geològic de Catalunya

LPL Lightning Protection Levels

LPS Lightning Protection System

LV Medium Voltage

Meteocat Servei Meteorològic de Catalunya

MPC Multiport Power Converter

MV Medium Voltage

NDVI Normalized Difference Vegetation Index

OPF Optimal Power Flow

PV Photovoltaics

RVI Distribution System Operator

TSO Transmission System Operator

VARI Visible Atmospherically Resistant Index

VIN Vegetation Index Number

XDDE Atmospheric Electrical Discharge Detection Network

Parameters

Δt Time-step of the model in [h]

$c_{BESS-b,i}$ Price of the battery energy storage b connected to the node i in [€/kWh]

$c_{buy-MG,i,t}$ Price of buying energy to the external grid MG connected to the node i at hour t in [€/kWh]

c_{conv-k} Cost of the multiport converter terminal k in [€/kW]

C_{en} Average annual energy price in [€/kWh]

$c_{sell-MG,i,t}$ Price of selling energy to the external grid MG connected to the node i at hour t in [€/kWh]

$E_{cap-b,i}$ Energy storage capacity of the battery b connected to the node i in [kWh]

f Number of buses in the system

k Weight to ponderate terms in the objective function

M Number of hazards included in the database

N_d Number of representative days

$P(A)$ Probability of event A

$P(B)$ Probability of event B

$p_{load-x,t}$ Power demanded by the load located at bus x at time t

$r_{i,k}$ Resistance of the line between nodes i, k in [p.u.]

S_b Base power of the system in [kW]

w Number of power lines in the system

w_d Weight of each representative day in the year

T Amount of time steps

BESS Battery Energy Storage System

Variables

ΔV Voltage drop along the year in [p.u.]

\mathcal{R}	Resilience Index
C_{BESS}	Battery energy storage cost in [€]
C_{MG}	Cost of energy exchange with the external grid in [€]
C_{MPC}	Multiport converter cost in [€]
E_{loss}	annual line losses in [kWh]
F	Function or variable that the MPC aims to improve
$i_{i,k,t,d}$	Current of the line between nodes i, k at hour t of the day d in [p.u.]
I_T	Aggregated element's impact
m_{BESS}	Minor term in the objective function
$P_{buy-MG,i,t,d}$	Active power bought from the external grid in [kW]
$P_{buy-MG,i,t}$	Active power bought from the external grid MG connected to the node i at hour t in [kW]
$P_{g,i,t,d}$	Active power provided by the generator g connected to the node i at hour t of the day d in [kW]
$P_{n,MPC-k,i}$	Active nominal power of the multiport converter terminal k connected to the node i in [kW]
$P_{sell-MG,i,t,d}$	Active power sold to the external grid in [kW]
$P_{sell-MG,i,t}$	Active power sold to the external grid MG connected to the node i at hour t in [kW]
R_T	Total energy / power at risk in the system
$S_{n,MPC-k,i}$	Apparent nominal power of the multiport converter terminal k connected to the node i in [kVA]
V_{4-5}	voltage difference between the buses to which the MPC will be connected along the year in [p.u.]
$v_{i,t,d}$	Voltage magnitude of node i at hour t of the day d in [p.u.]
$P_{char-b,i,t}$	Active charging power of the battery b connected to the node i at hour t in [kW]
$P_{disch-b,i,t}$	Active discharging power of the battery b connected to the node i at hour t in [kW]

1 Executive summary

Multiport Power Converters (MPC) are presented as a general power electronics solution for enhancing power operation in the distribution networks. MPCs might integrate three or more applications into a single device. In a context where the energy transition requires the introduction of converters in power systems, MPCs emerge as a promising technology to facilitate its integration while keeping projects economically feasible.

Until now, iPlug project explored various applications of MPCs in power systems and evaluated its more convenient topologies and developed specific methodologies to size, locate, and operate these converters. Based on the work of WP1, this document evaluated the MPCs inclusion in multiple real networks. Thus, six specific use cases are investigated.

Three use cases are applied to buildings, where the MPC is integrated into the consumer's electrical network. An energy-based optimization is applied to find the nominal power of the MPC terminals connected to PV, Battery Energy Storage System (BESS), Electric Vehicle (EV), other electric loads and the main grid. Furthermore, a cost analysis is also performed to identify when the MPC will be more cost-effective than traditional solutions and when the BESS will be economically feasible.

One use case investigates the role of the MPC in a LV electrical network with different voltage levels and potential to integrate PV and EV. A grid-based optimization is applied to find the nominal power of the MPC terminals and analyze the system performance. Different scenarios of MPC, PV and EV penetration are also compared.

Another study case is focused on a MV network. The grid-based optimization is applied to introduce the MPC into the network. In this case, a first analysis is performed on a simple network and later a real use case is analyzed. Several MPC scenarios are analyzed by changing the objective function and loads of the system.

Finally, an MPC is investigated from a resilience perspective. This use case examines the base resilience of an actual MV electrical network. This analysis requires accurate research about the hazards that might impact the system and the system's vulnerabilities. Based on the results, it is explored the most convenient application of the MPC to maximize resilience increase and risk reduction.

2 Introduction

The energy transition is transforming the power system. Modern power systems are evolving as decentralized and power converters are becoming dominant. In that regard, MPC is an innovative technology that might play a relevant role in contemporary power systems because of its ability to combine several converters into one and manage several issues.

This work investigates how the MPC can improve real networks from both sizing and resilience perspectives.

Optimal design of the MPC is important to avoid oversizing and obtain lower costs. Moreover, the MPC can provide different services to improve the system operation, for example losses reduction, integration of PV and Electric Vehicle (EV), improvement of voltage levels, and networks interconnection. This topic is addressed in Section 3, where an optimization-based methodology that finds the nominal power of the MPC and analyses the system operation is applied to several use cases. Section 3.1 analyses three cases where the MPC is used to integrate different appliances in buildings, including PV, EV and Battery Energy Storage System (BESS). Sections 3.2 and 3.3 analyse LV and MV use cases where the MPC is used to interconnect two networks and improve their performance, also PV and EV can be integrated in the MPC.

Finally, a resilience-driven use case explores the MPC from a resilient perspective. In recent years, resilience emerged as a new concept in complex systems. Thus, resilience is becoming a relevant concept in the future electrical network's planning and operation. This work considers that it is crucial to investigate the concept and the technologies that could be significant in its improvement, even though there are several definitions of resilience and there are no standardized procedures for them. In Section 4, this work presents a rural network connected to the main grid through a single connection point. The population in the region is relatively low and the demand is limited. Although the economic impact of outages in those grids is usually insignificant, the network's strength is crucial to keep the population in those territories. The work presented in this document examines the hazards that might affect the system and its vulnerabilities. From this initial investigation, the actual system's resilience is investigated. Then, the MPC is integrated into the system to evaluate how it might contribute to risk reduction and resilience increase. Among the various applications explored for the MPC, in the use case, the MPC is used to interconnect two MW power lines, using two AC ports, and to integrate a BESS as a backup, through an additional DC port.

Although each use case summarizes the main conclusions drawn from its investigation, Section 5 summarizes the most relevant highlights of this work.

3 Use cases for MPC sizing analysis

3.1 Building use cases

The first group of use cases involves household installations where MPC could improve power conversion efficiency and reduce the integration cost of batteries, solar panels and some appliances. Three different use cases are considered with hourly data from 2023 and 2024 provided by ICAT.

3.1.1 Use cases data

This section presents the detailed information of three different building use cases: Castelló d’Empúries health center, Garrotxa Regional Hospital, and ICAT headquarters.

Castelló d’Empúries health center has a 12 kW PV installation for self-consumption with surpluses compensation, meaning that the excess can be sold. The load profile, PV generation and electricity prices considered are shown in Figure 1, a constant sell price of 55 €/MWh is also supposed. Additionally, this building includes an electric generator of 51 kW nominal power and 57.8 kW maximum power as backup, but it is not considered in the current study.

Figure 1: Electric load, available PV and electricity buy price of Castelló d’Empúries health center from February 2023 to January 2024

Garrotxa Regional Hospital (Olot) has a 220 kW PV installation that works as self-consumption without surpluses compensation, therefore no power injections to the external grid are supposed. In addition to the main electric load, this use case also has EV loads. The load profiles, PV generation and electricity prices considered are shown in Figure 2. Also, this building has 4 generator sets of 780 kVA

each as backup, but they are not considered in the current study.

Figure 2: Electric and EV loads, available PV and electricity buy price of Garrotxa Regional Hospital from 2023 and 2024

ICAT headquarters also includes EV loads and 83 kW PV with surpluses compensation. The profiles of the loads, PV generation and electricity prices considered are shown in Figure 3, and a constant sell price of 37.5 €/MWh is supposed. This building also has a genset of 458 kW as backup, but it is not considered in the current study.

Figure 3: Electric and EV loads, available PV and electricity buy price of ICAT headquarters from 2023

3.1.2 Optimization

After defining the use cases, the sizing of the converters or multiport converter required is addressed. To perform this analysis, the methodology mentioned in iPlug’s Deliverable 1.2 Section 3 is applied. This methodology (Figure 4) consists in an energetic optimization of the system, therefore, considering only active power and no grid constraints. Where the 1-year historical data of the loads and renewable sources is supposed to represent a perfect forecast for the years studied.

Figure 4: Flowchart of the energy-based MPC sizing methodology

The objective of the optimization in the building use cases, is to minimize the total cost of the system in 30 years, including the cost of the multiport converter (C_{MPC}), battery energy storage systems (C_{BESS}), and energy from the external grid (C_{MG}). Additionally, to avoid the battery charging and

discharging at the same time, the minor term m_{BESS} is considered. These terms are expressed as:

$$C_{MPC} = \sum_{k,i} c_{conv-k} \cdot P_{n,MPC-k,i} \quad (1)$$

$$C_{BESS} = \sum_{k,i} c_{BESS-b,i} \cdot E_{cap-b,i} \quad (2)$$

$$C_{MG} = \sum_{MG,i} \sum_{t=0}^T (P_{buy-MG,i,t} \cdot c_{buy-MG,i,t} - P_{sell-MG,i,t} \cdot c_{sell-MG,i,t}) \cdot \Delta t \quad (3)$$

$$m_{BESS} = 0.01 \cdot \sum_{b,i} \sum_{t=0}^T (P_{char-b,i,t} + P_{disch-b,i,t}) \quad (4)$$

where $P_{n,MPC-k,i}$ is the active nominal power of each multiport converter terminal k connected to the node i , c_{conv-k} is the price of the multiport converter terminal k , $E_{cap-b,i}$ is the energy storage capacity of the battery b connected to the node i , $c_{BESS-b,i}$ is the price of the battery storage, $P_{buy-MG,i,t}$ and $P_{sell-MG,i,t}$ are the active power bought and sold to the external grid MG connected to the node i at hour t , $c_{buy-MG,i,t}$ and $c_{sell-MG,i,t}$ are the prices for buying and selling power to the external grid, $P_{char-b,i,t}$ and $P_{disch-b,i,t}$ are the active charging and discharging powers of the battery energy storage, Δt is the calculation period, which is 1 h, and T is the amount of time steps in the year, which has a value of 8760.

Therefore, the objective function can be expressed as:

$$[min] C_{MPC} + C_{BESS} + C_{MG} \cdot t_{life} + m_{BESS} \quad (5)$$

where t_{life} is a factor to weight the capex and opex terms, supposed as 30 years, which is similar to the multiport converter lifetime. The multiport converter weighting price is 150 €/kW for each terminal, and the battery price is 750 €/kWh [3].

3.1.3 Results and discussion

This section focuses on the use of MPC to integrate several elements in a single device. Therefore 3 scenarios are defined to compare different MPC connections (Figure 5):

- Scenario A: traditional approach that considers single converters instead of MPC. To adapt the methodology to this scenario, the same inputs as scenario B are considered changing the cost to 0 for the terminal connected to the load and external grid.
- Scenario B: the AC loads and external grid connection are connected through the same MPC terminal.
- Scenario C: the AC loads and external grid connection are connected through different MPC

terminals.

Figure 5: Building use cases scenarios

The results of applying the energy-based multiport converter sizing optimization to the building use cases are shown in Tables 3 to 5. As expected, the nominal power of terminals directly connected to loads is the peak load, PV is usually a bit curtailed (less than 0.3 %), and battery energy storage is always zero. Comparing the scenarios, the biggest difference is found on the connection of the main load and external grid. If there is no storage, the AC load is mainly supplied by the external grid since the PV is comparatively small. Therefore, having the AC loads and the external grid in different terminals leads to a much higher MPC nominal power than having them connected in the same MPC terminal. Concluding that scenario C is more expensive than scenario B. Moreover, in Scenario B, the PV is directly determining the nominal power of the terminal connected to the grid, as the EV load is non-existent or significantly lower.

Table 3: Nominal power of the MPC terminals of Castelló d’Empúries health center

Scenario A		Scenario B		Scenario C	
		Loads + grid	9.2 kW	Loads	52.95 kW
PV	9.38 kW	PV	9.2 kW	PV	9.39 kW
BESS	0 kW	BESS	0 kW	BESS	0 kW
				Grid	49.94 kW

Table 4: Nominal power of the MPC terminals of Garrotxa Regional Hospital

Scenario A		Scenario B		Scenario C	
		Loads + grid	157.5 kW	Loads	1028.15 kW
EV	20.16 kW	EV	20.16 kW	EV	20.16 kW
PV	161 kW	PV	157.5 kW	PV	161 kW
BESS	0 kW	BESS	0 kW	BESS	0 kW
				Grid	951.75 kW

Table 5: Nominal power of the MPC terminals of ICAT headquarters

Scenario A		Scenario B		Scenario C	
		Loads + grid	63.6 kW	Loads	301.8 kW
EV	20.33 kW	EV	20.33 kW	EV	20.33 kW
PV	65.2 kW	PV	63.6 kW	PV	65.2 kW
BESS	0 kW	BESS	0 kW	BESS	0 kW
				Grid	295 kW

Since the MPC enables the operation of different elements, the change in its cost will have an impact mainly on PV utilization. Converter cost changes will have a similar impact in terms of power in both Scenario A and B, although the total cost will be different. Figures 6 and 7 shows how the MPC cost weight affects the sizing of the terminals in Scenario A and B respectively. Figure 8 shows the total MPC or converter cost of Scenarios A and B according to their prices. These plots can be translated to quite accurate regressions shown in Table 6, where c_{MPC} and c_{conv} are the MPC and converter prices.

Figure 6: Nominal power of the AC/DC converter connected to the PV of the building use cases in Scenario A according to the weighting cost of the converters

Figure 7: Nominal power of the MPC terminals connected to PV, external grid and loads of the building use cases in Scenario B according to the weighting cost of the MPC terminals

Figure 8: Total cost of AC/DC converters (Scenario A) or the MPC (Scenario B) of the building use cases according to their unitary cost

Table 6: Regressions of the Scenario A and B costs with respect to the power electronics unitary costs for the building use cases

	Scenario A	Scenario B
Castelló d'Empúries health center	$9.1457 \cdot c_{conv} + 29.575$	$17.759 \cdot c_{MPC} + 81.07$
Garrotxa Regional Hospital	$177.26 \cdot c_{conv} + 517.53$	$323.86 \cdot c_{MPC} + 1502.4$
ICAT headquarters	$83.553 \cdot c_{conv} + 267.25$	$142.43 \cdot c_{MPC} + 678.06$

Comparing Scenarios A and B, it is clear that the MPC will have a higher total power than the sum of all VSC from Scenario A. However, the MPC is expected to reduce the amount power electronics and it can present alternative options to AC/DC configurations that are expected to reduce cost. After analysing the cost sensitivity in Scenario A and B, a cost relationship can be calculated to find when the MPC will be economically the best option. Figure 9 shows the costs relationships between MPC and AC/DC converter costs, where the green area represents those cases where Scenario B will have lower total costs than Scenario A. Therefore, the MPC cost should be between 43 and 55 % less than the converter cost, depending on the case and for a range between 50 and 250 €/kW, to be economically feasible. Comparing the three use cases, it can also be concluded that the MPC will become increasingly economically better with more elements connected to it, specially if they have similar power range.

Figure 9: Relationship between MPC and AC/DC converter costs

An important consideration regarding this conclusion is that the methodology applied considers separately the sizing of the different MPC terminals. Different results would be obtained if the inter-connections between terminals would be considered in the sizing, such as the methodology presented in [4].

The results show that battery energy storage is never cost-effective. For that reason, a sensitivity analysis with the parameters of Table 7 is performed on Scenario B to find when the BESS will be economically feasible. This sensitivity analysis considers different MPC and BESS costs, as well as an escalating factor on the cost of energy from the external grid. Results show that the most relevant parameters are the BESS and energy costs. In these use cases, the battery is only used to reduce operational costs, and usually all the PV generation goes to supply the loads rather than injecting to the external grid. In that sense, the available PV generation represents less than 16.4 %, 6 % and 14 % of the annual load in the ICAT headquarters, Garrotxa Regional Hospital and Castelló d'Empúries health center respectively. Also, without BESS, ICAT headquarters would inject less than 3 GWh in a year (up to 320 kWh in a single day) and Castelló d'Empúries health center would inject less than 200 kWh/year (up to 50 kWh/day), while Garrotxa Regional Hospital would never inject power. Therefore, storage is more interesting with higher energy prices and lower BESS costs, as shown in Figure 10, where those cases without BESS are not plotted. Further results on storage capacity and C-rate of the BESS, as well as the nominal power of the multiport converter terminals are presented in Appendix D.1.

Table 7: Sensitivity analysis parameters

Parameters	Start	Step	End
MPC cost [€/kW]	100	10	200
BESS cost [€/kWh]	100	50	800
Energy cost factor	0.1	0.1	3

Figure 10: BESS storage capacity of ICAT headquarters considering sensitivity parameters of Table 7

3.2 LV use case

The second group of study cases includes applications where MPC interconnect two or more networks in order to achieve better power management. These LV distribution networks also have potential for adoption of distributed renewable energy capacity. This section presents a case where the MPC is used in the interconnection between multiple LV lines at different voltage levels.

3.2.1 System definition

The following scenario considers the interconnection of two LV lines, operating at 400 V and 230 V. Furthermore, the network has the potential to install up to 100 kW solar generation and some EV.

The topology of these LV networks is shown in Figure 11, with the loads provided by Anell. These networks have a relatively big amount of buses and despite their radial structure, they present low voltage drops in normal operation. For these reasons, the topology has been simplified to reduce the computational requirements. The simplified topology shown in Figure 12 considers only the path between the MPC and the MV grid, reducing the number of buses from 78 and 57 to 9 and 5 respectively, and the loads have been aggregated to the buses in that path. These buses have been renamed as shown in Table 8. Additionally, an extra load has been added to buses 2 and 11 that connect with the MV grid to match the supervisors and meters data provided by Anell. In the resulting network, the buses without loads have not been considered, and the simplified lines have an impedance equal to the sum of the original lines, and maximum current equal to the minimum of the original lines. Tables 9 and 10 present the parameters of the simplified topology. The maximum current is supposed 344 A for all lines, as the loads could not be supplied considering some of the maximum currents provided by Anell.

Figure 11: Complete topology of Anell LV grids with potential MPC

Figure 12: Simplified topology of Anell LV grids with potential MPC

Table 8: List of buses of LV use case

Bus id	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
Bus name	62662	62914	63072	63197	63295	63334	63409	63692

Bus id	11	12	13	14
Bus name	63590	63725	63922	63784

Table 9: Line parameters of LV use case

From bus	To bus	R [mΩ]	X [mΩ]
2	3	14.94	16.8
3	4	9.5	10.66
4	5	4.6	5.15
5	6	2.78	3.1
6	7	3.94	4.41
7	8	3.18	3.55
8	9	4.73	5.28
11	12	3.95	3.01
12	13	8.91	10
13	14	26.64	29.92

Table 10: Transformer parameters of LV use case

V_2 [V]	Z_{tr} to V_2 side [mΩ]	S_{rated} [kVA]
400	8.7+j21.75	250
230	1.64+j5.39	400

In addition of interconnecting two networks, the MPC can also integrate different appliances. In this case, the system has the potential to install up to 100 kW of PV, which would be connected to a DC terminal of the MPC. The PV generation availability has been extracted from PVGIS [5] for the area where the LV networks are located. Also, an EV charging station could be connected to the MPC. This use case also aims to analyze the impact of including an EV charger to the grid. Anell provided data from 2018 to 2021 of an example EV charging station, although all other system loads correspond to the year 2023. However, the data shows a low usage of the EV charger. For this reason, a theoretical EV profile equal to the sum of the 4 years of available data is used, resulting in a maximum power of around 7 kW.

3.2.2 Methodology

In this use case, the sizing of the multiport converter is performed with a grid-based optimization, mentioned in iPlug’s Deliverable 1.2 Section 3. This methodology, similar to that of Section 3.1.2 including both active and reactive power and grid constraints. Performing this optimization for 1-year data would be computationally infeasible to solve with the available resources. For this reason, only a few representative days are considered.

The objective of the optimization in the LV use case is to size the multiport converter while improving the grid operation. The objective function will include different terms:

- Minimize the multiport converter cost (C_{MPC}) which is expressed as:

$$C_{MPC} = \sum_{k,i} c_{conv-k} \cdot S_{n,MPC-k,i} \quad (6)$$

where $S_{n,MPC-k,i}$ is the apparent nominal power of each multiport converter terminal k connected to the node i , and its cost is 150 €/kVA.

- Maximize annual PV generation, which is expressed as:

$$E_{ren} = \frac{1}{\sum_{d=1}^{N_d} w_d} \cdot \sum_{d=1}^{N_d} w_d \cdot 365 \sum_{t=0}^T \sum_{g,i} P_{g,i,t,d} \cdot \Delta t \quad (7)$$

where $P_{g,i,t,d}$ is the active power provided by the generator g connected to the node i at hour t of the day d , T corresponds to the 24 h in each day, N_d is the number of representative days, and w_d is the weight of each representative day in the year.

- Minimize the annual line losses (E_{loss}) which is expressed as:

$$E_{loss} = \frac{1}{\sum_{d=1}^{N_d} w_d} \cdot \sum_{d=1}^{N_d} w_d \cdot 365 \cdot \sum_{t=0}^T \sum_{i,k} i_{i,k,t,d}^2 \cdot r_{i,k} \cdot S_b \cdot \Delta t \quad (8)$$

where $i_{i,k,t,d}$ and $r_{i,k}$ are the current and resistance of the line between bus i and k , and S_b is the base power of the system.

- Minimize the voltage drop (ΔV) which is expressed as:

$$\Delta V = \frac{1}{\sum_{d=1}^{N_d} w_d} \cdot \sum_{d=1}^{N_d} w_d \cdot 365 \sum_{t=0}^T \sum_i |v_{i,t,d} - 1| \quad (9)$$

where $v_{i,t,d}$ is the voltage magnitude of node i at hour t of the day d .

- Additionally, to avoid exporting and importing energy from the external grids at the same time, the minor term m_{MG} is considered, which is expressed as:

$$m_{MG} = 0.00001 \cdot \frac{1}{\sum_{d=1}^{N_d} w_d} \cdot \sum_{d=1}^{N_d} w_d \cdot \sum_{MG,i} \sum_{t=0}^T (P_{buy-MG,i,t,d} + P_{sell-MG,i,t,d}) \quad (10)$$

where $P_{buy-MG,i,t,d}$ and $P_{sell-MG,i,t,d}$ are the active power bought and sold to the external grid.

Therefore, the objective function can be expressed as:

$$[min] C_{MPC} + (E_{ren} \cdot C_{en} + E_{loss} + \Delta V) \cdot t_{life} + m_{MG} \quad (11)$$

where investment and annual terms are weighted considering an MPC lifetime (t_{life}) of 20 years, C_{en} is the average annual energy price, supposed as 50 €/MWh

The representative days’ selection methodology proposes using the idea of clusters to reduce the amount of data. In this report, an Autoencoder model for the clustering of time-series data is proposed. However, several other clustering or classification algorithms and software could be considered to improve the representative days’ selection. The autoencoders are a method of unsupervised feedforward neural network that can be applied to capture accurately the key aspects of the dataset provided to provide a compressed version of the input data. The autoencoders are based on the same principles as artificial neural networks (ANNs). The clustering methodology proposed is shown in Figure 13 and based in [6].

Figure 13: Flowchat of the Autoencoder-based methodology

3.2.3 Representative days selection

The available data provided by Anell includes all hourly profiles of the loads from May 2nd to August 31st of 2023, excluding a few days. To reduce the computational requirements regarding the data resolution, an unsupervised clustering methodology for time-series data [6] is applied. In this use case, 6 time series are considered, including total active and reactive power load of each network, PV available generation and EV load.

The algorithm calculates how good is the clustering and then selects the amount of clusters that fits best. However, for this case, it is interesting to have as many clusters as possible, to improve the quality of the analysis, as long as there is no negligible cluster and the clustering is still good.

Comparing the weight distribution for different clustering numbers, 7 clusters were chosen. Finally,

one day belonging to each cluster must be chosen to use in the optimization process. There are several ways to do this, from simply picking the first day of each cluster to choose the most average day inside each cluster. However, in this case the day with the biggest EV load was chosen, as the EV profiles of this use case are quite sparse. This results in the clusters, weights and representative days presented in Table 11. The loads and available generation of the selected days are shown in Figure 14.

Table 11: Representative days of the LV use case

Class	Weight	Date			
Day 1	17.98 %	4th May			
Day 2	29.01 %	18th June			
Day 6	6.84 %	28th June			
Day 3	11.97 %	29th June			
Day 7	7.69 %	19th July			
Day 5	6.84 %	21st July </tr <tr> <td>Day 4</td> <td>19.66 %</td> <td>30th July</td> </tr>	Day 4	19.66 %	30th July
Day 4	19.66 %	30th July			

Figure 14: Electric loads for each bus, available PV and EV load of LV use case, where the seven representative days have been presented consecutively

3.2.4 Results and discussion

This section analyzes the performance obtained from applying the grid-based multiport converter sizing optimization to the LV use case. Moreover, several scenarios are considered to better understand the effects of the MPC, as well as the PV and EV, on the grid.

The initial scenario only considers the 400 V and 230 V networks, without interconnection. Then different scenarios with MPC installation are considered. First, a two-terminal MPC is introduced connecting bus 8 to port 1 and bus 13 to port 2. In this scenario, the MPC operates similar to a SOP. Later, a 100 kW PV generator and the EV shown in Figure 14 are introduced. In this scenario, a four-terminal MPC is considered, where port 3 is connected to the PV and port 4 to the EV. Finally, two scenarios with extreme PV and EV are analyzed, where PV is doubled and EV is four times the previous one.

Initial scenario. Figure 15 shows that the 230 V network has an overall higher active power import of energy and always imports reactive power, while the 400 V network sometimes imports and sometimes exports reactive power. Figures 16 and 17 shows the line current and bus voltages, where the lines colored from blue to green represent the 400 V network, whereas the red to yellow colors represent the 230 V network. The first line of each network are carrying big currents, then the second line of each network also has a significant current, and all the other lines have comparatively small currents. This is expected, as the biggest loads are connected to the first and second buses of each network. The voltages range from 0.99 to 1 p.u. in both networks, although most of the time they are around 0.996 p.u. The first bus of both networks has a significant voltage drop, then the voltage drop is negligible from the third bus of the 400 V network, whereas the 230 V network presents low voltage drops from the second bus.

Figure 15: Active and reactive power import from the external grid for LV use case in the initial scenario

Figure 16: Line currents for LV use case in the initial scenario

Figure 17: Bus voltages for LV use case in the initial scenario

Two-terminal MPC scenario (SOP). Results show that only a small converter is required in this scenario, with around 2.3 kVA each terminal (Table 12). For this reason, the obtained results regarding the network operation are similar to those of the initial scenario. Figure 18 shows that the MPC flows power in both directions, although usually power goes from the 230 V to the 400 V network. Also, both MPC ports provide reactive power usually in a constant way, and only port 1 absorbs some reactive power a few hours on the first day. As a result, the MPC slightly increases the voltages in both networks. Further results of this scenario are presented in Appendix D.2.

Figure 18: Active and reactive power of the MPC terminals for LV use case in the two-terminal MPC scenario

Four-terminal MPC scenario. Due to the incorporation of the PV, the 400 V network exports some active power, although the 230 V network is importing at the same time (Figure 19). The PV generation is injected to both networks through the MPC, for that reason the currents and voltage levels increase significantly in the buses close to the MPC, specially on the 400 V network (Figures 20 and 21). The MPC integrates efficiently the PV generation, as shown in Figure 22, by injecting twice as much power to the 400 V network than to the 230 V network with the objective of minimizing the losses. The EV is also effectively integrated in the MPC, although it represents only a small load, most of the time the EV is supplied by the PV. In this scenario, the MPC also has an important role in reactive power management, as it provides around 1.5 kvar to the 230 V network, and can provide or absorb up to 6

kvar to the 400 V network. Resulting in a MPC of around 136 kVA (Table 12), summing the nominal power of each terminal. It can be concluded that the nominal power of the MPC terminals, except the one connected to the EV, is directly related to the amount of PV connected to the MPC. In fact, some PV curtailment appears in order to provide the best techno-economic solution of the MPC.

Figure 19: Active and reactive power import from the external grid for LV use case in the four-terminal MPC scenario

Figure 20: Line currents for LV use case in the four-terminal MPC scenario

Figure 21: Bus voltages for LV use case in the four-terminal MPC scenario

Figure 22: Active and reactive power of the MPC terminals for LV use case in the four-terminal MPC scenario

Extreme PV scenario. With higher PV penetration, the active power exportations increase in both networks, also the currents and voltages increase in the same way as mentioned in the four-terminal MPC scenario. Also as before, the PV power injected from the MPC to the 230 V network is around half of the PV power injected to the 400 V network. As mentioned before, the nominal power of the MPC is directly related to the amount of PV, but in this scenario the PV curtailment has increased as observed in Figure 23. Further results of this scenario are presented in Appendix D.2.

Figure 23: Active and reactive power of the MPC terminals for LV use case in the extreme PV scenario

Extreme EV scenario. The EV load, even considering four times the base one, is small compared to the PV generation. And the MPC is mainly sized according to the amount of PV connected, as seen in the previous scenarios. Therefore, this scenario has similar results to those of the four-terminal MPC scenario, with only slight differences during the EV load peaks and mainly increasing the nominal power of the MPC terminal connected to the EV. All results of this scenario are presented in Appendix D.2.

Indicators. In addition to the system operation, a few indicators have been considered. In particular the nominal power of the MPC terminals and the different terms of the objective function are analyzed, all these indicators are presented in Table 12. Without PV, the best techno-economic solution is to have only a small two-terminal MPC and connecting both networks does not make big differences compared to the initial scenario, as losses and voltage drop only decrease slightly. Introducing PV and EV loads to the system is what makes the MPC an interesting solution. The nominal power of the MPC terminal

connected to the EV corresponds to the peak load and the nominal power of the other MPC terminals is directly related to the amount of PV, as mentioned before. In that sense, the four-terminal MPC scenario has only 3 % of PV curtailment, compared with the almost 11 % of the extreme PV scenario. This enables to reduce the nominal power of the MPC terminal connected to the PV around 20 % in the four-terminal MPC scenario and around 37 % in the extreme PV scenario, resulting in the most cost-effective solution. Introducing the PV also increases the losses due to the export capacity of the system. On the other hand, combining the PV and the MPC reduces the voltage drop of the system. With increasing PV penetration, losses increase and voltage drop decreases further. Regarding the EV, increasing its presence mainly provides that the nominal power of the MPC terminal connected to it increases, while losses and the voltage drop increase slightly. In the four-terminal MPC scenario, the MPC follows the specifications shown in Table 13.

Table 12: Indicators for the different scenarios of the LV use case

	Initial	SOP	MPC	Extreme PV	Extreme EV
E_{loss} [kWh]	1607.8	1599.8	2150.84	4148.75	2179.44
ΔV	2311.14	2271.73	2081.04	1931.9	2110.21
E_{ren} [MWh]	-	-	126.69	233.38	126.91
Port 1 nominal power [kVA]	-	2.35	44.05	69.36	44.42
Port 2 nominal power [kVA]	-	2.29	19.49	29.78	19.63
Port 3 nominal power [kVA]	-	-	64.26	101.2	64.79
Port 4 nominal power [kVA]	-	-	8.4	8.4	33.6
MPC nominal power [kVA]	-	4.64	136.2	208.74	162.43

Table 13: Specification table of the MPC for the LV use case

AC Port 1			
U_n (RMS)	400	V	
I_n (RMS)	63.5	A	
S_n (RMS)	44	kVA	
AC Port 2			
U_n (RMS)	230	V	
I_n (RMS)	50.2	A	
S_n (RMS)	20	kVA	
DC Port 3			
P_n	65	kW	
DC Port 4			
P_n	9	kW	

3.3 MV use case

The third group of study cases includes applications where MPC interconnect two buses of a MV network with load imbalances. This section presents a first analysis of the general concept of subtransmission grid, and a specific use case provided by Anell.

3.3.1 Analysis of the general concept

The general concept of MV network is presented in Figure 24. This network can have two lines with same or different voltage levels, and can be connected through a transformer or line. The MV network can also be called subtransmission network if it is an intermediate link between distribution and transmission networks, and operates at lower levels than the transmission network. The MPC is introduced in this network to improve the power management and reduce the voltage drop differences, moreover it can integrate additional loads and renewable generation, such as EV and PV.

Figure 24: Subtransmission grid concept

To develop a first analysis on this concept, the previous figure has been simplified to Figure 25. If z_1 and z_2 were equal, L_2 and L_3 would have the same power factor, and the objective was to balance the load or minimize the voltage difference between bus 2 and 3 through an interconnection of those buses, then the best solution would be to introduce a two-terminal MPC that can transfer the amount of power shown in (12).

Figure 25: Simple MV topology

$$P_{MPC} = \frac{|L_2 - L_3|}{2} \tag{12}$$

The same network of Figure 25 can be considered to analyse the impact that different objectives can have on the sizing of the two-terminal MPC. In that sense, the methodology presented in iPlug's

Deliverable 1.2 Section 3 has been applied. The network parameters considered are shown in Table 14. Several combinations of L_1 and L_2 loads are considered, with each load between 2 and 12 MW. These loads are considered for a single time-step, therefore all hours of the year would be equal regarding the optimization. Moreover, the need to incorporate an MPC to the network will be measured based on the voltage difference between bus 2 and 3 when there is no interconnection (initial configuration).

Table 14: Parameters of the simple MV use case

V	20 kV
S base	25 MVA
Z_1	$0.016+1.92j \Omega$
Z_2	$1.4028+2.0048j \Omega$
Z_3	$2.499+1.7934j \Omega$
Loads PF	0.98

The objective function is defined as:

$$[\min] C_{MPC} + F \cdot k \cdot t_{life} \quad (13)$$

where the MPC lifetime (t_{life}) is 20 years, F is the function or variable that the MPC aims to improve, C_{MPC} is the MPC cost weight that follows (6), and k is a weight to ponderate the two terms of the objective function.

In a first scenario, the objective of introducing the MPC will be to reduce the power losses in the lines, therefore F has the expression presented in (8). Figure 26 shows that the MPC nominal power tends to increase linearly with higher voltage differences between the buses before their interconnection. In the second scenario, the objective is to reduce the voltage drop of all buses, therefore F has the expression presented in (9). In this scenario, Figure 27 shows that there is no clear relationship between the MPC nominal power and the voltage differences between the buses before their interconnection, and the weight factor of the objective function terms has a huge impact on the results. Further results on these two scenarios are presented in Appendix D.3.1.

Figure 26: Nominal power of the MPC with respect to the voltage difference between the buses before their interconnection, for different weights on the objective function, for the simple MV use case in the first scenario

Figure 27: Nominal power of the MPC with respect to the voltage difference between the buses before their interconnection, for different weights on the objective function, for the simple MV use case in the second scenario

In the last scenario, the objective is to reduce the voltage difference between buses 2 and 3, to which the MPC will be connected, therefore F is expressed as:

$$F = \frac{1}{\sum_{d=1}^{N_d} w_d} \cdot \sum_{d=1}^{N_d} w_d \cdot 365 \sum_{t=0}^T |v_{2,t,d} - v_{3,t,d}| \quad (14)$$

This scenario presents a linear trend between the voltage difference between the buses before their interconnection and the MPC nominal power, as Figure 28 shows that MPC nominal power increases with a higher initial voltage difference. Also, the MPC reactive power management is increasingly important with lower initial voltages (Figure 29). If the weight factor k is high enough, such as 140, then, as a result, buses 2 and 3 have the same voltage when the MPC is connected, but lower values of k can lead to different voltages on bus 2 and 3.

Figure 28: Nominal power of the MPC with respect to the voltage difference between the buses before their interconnection, for different weights on the objective function, for the simple MV use case in the third scenario

Figure 29: Power factor of the MPC according to the voltage of the buses before their interconnection, for the simple MV use case in the third scenario

3.3.2 Anell MV system

The following scenario considers the interconnection of two MV lines operating at 40 kV. The topology of this network is shown in Figure 30, with the loads provided by Anell. Based on the line parameters, and supposing that the switch between buses 4 and 6 is open, the topology can be simplified as Figure 31, with the parameters presented in Table 15, to reduce computational requirements. The MPC is introduced in this network to reduce the voltage difference between two buses.

Figure 30: Topology of the MV grid use case provided by Anell

Figure 31: Simplified topology of the MV grid use case provided by Anell

Table 15: Line parameters of LV use case

Line	R [Ω]	X [Ω]	I _{max} [kA]
L_0	0.7758	7.7584	18.73
L_1	1.1832	1.3517	0.315
L_2	2.4329	2.7595	0.315
L_3	2.5865	3.0808	0.315
L_4	3.225	3.8381	0.315

The available data provided by Anell includes hourly profiles of the loads for 80 days between November 1st of 2023 and September 9th of 2024. As before, the clustering methodology of [6] is applied to reduce computational requirements. In this use case, 8 time series are considered, including total active and reactive power of each load. This results in the clusters, weights, and representative days presented in Table 16. The loads and available generation of the selected days are shown in Figure 32.

Table 16: Representative days of the MV use case

Class	Weight	Date
Day 1	3.75 %	1st November 2023
Day 2	5 %	2nd November 2023
Day 3	31.25 %	13th November 2023
Day 4	27.5 %	15th November 2023
Day 5	25 %	18th November 2023
Day 6	8.75 %	21st August 2024

Figure 32: Electric loads of MV use case, where the six representative days have been presented consecutively

In this use case, the sizing of the multiport converter is performed with a grid-based optimization, mentioned in iPlug’s Deliverable 1.2 Section 3. This methodology, similar to that of Section 3.2.2. The objective of the optimization in the MV use case is to size the multiport converter while improving the grid operation. In that sense, the objective function can be expressed as:

$$[\min] C_{MPC} + (E_{loss} + \Delta V + V_{4-5} \cdot k) \cdot t_{life} + m_{MG} \quad (15)$$

$$V_{4-5} = \frac{1}{\sum_{d=1}^{N_d} w_d} \cdot \sum_{d=1}^{N_d} w_d \cdot 365 \sum_{t=0}^T |v_{4,t,d} - v_{5,t,d}| \quad (16)$$

where investment and annual terms are weighted considering an MPC lifetime (t_{life}) of 30 years, V_{4-5} represents the voltage difference between the buses to which the MPC will be connected, and k is its additional weight factor, supposed as 1.

The results of applying this methodology to the MV use case are presented below, considering that the switches are in the positions shown in Figure 31. First, a scenario without the MPC is evaluated, and then a second scenario introducing the MPC is analyzed to understand the impact of the MPC on the network. Furthermore, a sensitivity analysis on the objective function weights has been performed, and an extreme load case has been analyzed.

Base case. The initial scenario, without the MPC, represents a radial topology. In this scenario, there is no current flowing from bus 2 to bus 4, therefore they have the same voltage. Also, Sant Pere load is very small, comparatively, therefore the voltage at buses 3 and 5 is very similar and the current between those buses is very low (Figure 36). Higher differences can be observed in Figure 33 between bus 2 and 3 voltages due to the different loads and line parameters. These differences mainly occur when the Patel load is at its peak and the Pujolà load is almost zero (Figure 34). However, as the network is oversized, the minimum voltage of the system is 0.993 p.u. and the maximum voltage difference between the buses to which the converter will be later connected is 0.0041 p.u..

Figure 33: Bus voltages for the MV use case in the initial scenario

Figure 34: Voltage difference between bus 4 and 5 for the MV use case in the initial scenario

Figure 35: Active and reactive power import from the external grid for the MV use case in the initial scenario

Figure 36: Line currents for the MV use case in the initial scenario

When the MPC is introduced, active power flows from bus 5 to bus 4, increasing significantly the currents of those lines (Figure 40). As shown in Figure 41, the MPC also provides reactive power to both sides, specially to bus 4. Comparing Figures 35 and 39, it is observed a reduction of reactive power imported from the HV network, which is equal to the total reactive power provided by the MPC. Altogether, the voltages tend to increase, except at bus 4 that decreases, with a minimum voltage of the system of 0.994 p.u. (Figure 37). The voltage difference between the buses to which the converter is connected is also reduced, with a maximum of 0.0015 p.u. (Figure 38).

Figure 37: Bus voltages for the MV use case in the MPC scenario

Figure 38: Voltage difference between bus 4 and 5 for the MV use case in the MPC scenario

Figure 39: Active and reactive power import from the external grid for the MV use case in the MPC scenario

Figure 40: Line currents for the MV use case in the MPC scenario

Figure 41: Active and reactive power of the MPC terminals for MV use case in the MPC scenario

The nominal power of the MPC terminals and the objective function terms are considered as indicators and presented in Table 17. In this use case, the nominal power of the MPC terminals is small compared with the loads, but it manages to slightly reduce the losses on the lines and the voltage difference between the buses to which it is connected while increasing the overall voltage levels. In this case, the MPC follows the specifications shown in Table 18.

Table 17: Indicators for the MV use case

	Initial	MPC
E_{loss} [MWh]	217.8	202.3
ΔV	155.1	141
V_{4-5}	23.91	15.84
V_{min}	0.993 p.u.	0.994 p.u.
Port 1 nominal power [kVA]	-	484.7
Port 2 nominal power [kVA]	-	468
MPC nominal power [kVA]	-	952.7

Table 18: Specification table of the MPC for the MV use case

AC Port 1			
U_n (RMS)	40	kV	
I_n (RMS)	7.07	A	
S_n (RMS)	490	kVA	
AC Port 2			
U_n (RMS)	40	kV	
I_n (RMS)	7.07	A	
S_n (RMS)	490	kVA	

Sensitivity analysis. As seen before, introducing the MPC reduces the voltage difference between the buses to which it is connected, but there is still some voltage difference. To analyse how the MPC size impacts this voltage difference, a sensitivity analysis has been performed on the k parameter from the objective function, as it indicates the importance of the voltage difference in the overall optimization. Higher values of k will lead to lower voltage differences and higher nominal power of the MPC terminals, as shown in Figure 42.

Figure 42: Nominal power of the MPC, as the sum of the nominal power of all terminals, and the voltage difference between the buses to which the MPC is connected, with respect to the k values of the colormap, for MV use case in the MPC scenario

Extreme load case The previous scenarios have high voltage levels in general, and the Sant Pere load does not play a significant role in the overall system. For this reason, the previous analysis has been repeated increasing the Sant Pere load by a factor of 500, so it will be on the same order of magnitude than Patel and Pujolà loads. In this case, k parameter is supposed as 0.

The initial scenario of this case presents significant voltage drops in buses 3 and 5, reaching up to 0.96 p.u. (Figure 43). And the maximum voltage difference between the buses to which the MPC will be connected reaches 0.036 p.u. at the peaks of the Sant Pere load (Figure 44). Also, an important increase of the currents between buses 1 and 5 is observed in Figure 46.

Figure 43: Bus voltages for the MV use case in the initial scenario with increased Sant Pere load

Figure 44: Voltage difference between bus 4 and 5 for the MV use case in the initial scenario with increased Sant Pere load

Figure 45: Active and reactive power import from the external grid for the MV use case in the initial scenario with increased Sant Pere load

Figure 46: Line currents for the MV use case in the initial scenario with increased Sant Pere load

Introducing the MPC enables to manage the power of the two sides so that currents now tend to be below 200 A (Figure 50). In this case, the MPC allows a significant active power flow mostly from bus 5 to bus 4, and provides important amounts of reactive power to bus 5 (Figure 51). This results in the voltages of the two sides getting closer, with a maximum voltage difference of 0.013 p.u. between the buses to which the converter (Figure 48) and a minimum voltage of 0.977 p.u. in the system (Figure 47).

Figure 47: Bus voltages for the MV use case in the MPC scenario with increased Sant Pere load

Figure 48: Voltage difference between bus 4 and 5 for the MV use case in the MPC scenario with increased Sant Pere load

Figure 49: Active and reactive power import from the external grid for the MV use case in the MPC scenario with increased Sant Pere load

Figure 50: Line currents for the MV use case in the MPC scenario with increased Sant Pere load

Figure 51: Active and reactive power of the MPC terminals for MV use case in the MPC scenario with increased Sant Pere load

As before, the nominal power of the MPC terminals and other indicators are presented in Table 19. In this case, the nominal power of the MPC terminals has the same order of magnitude than the system

loads, and the MPC provides significant improvements in both the voltage levels and the losses. In this case, the MPC follows the specifications shown in Table 20.

Table 19: Indicators for the MV use case with increased Sant Pere load

	Initial	MPC
E_{loss} [MWh]	772.05	508.44
ΔV	358.28	274.5
V_{4-5}	131.91	7.07
V_{min}	0.96 p.u.	0.977 p.u.
Port 1 nominal power [MVA]	-	3.089
Port 2 nominal power [MVA]	-	3.261
MPC nominal power [MVA]	-	6.350

Table 20: Specification table of the MPC for the MV use case with increased Sant Pere load

AC Port 1			
U_n (RMS)	40	kV	
I_n (RMS)	47.6	A	
S_n (RMS)	3.3	MVA	
AC Port 2			
U_n (RMS)	40	kV	
I_n (RMS)	47.6	A	
S_n (RMS)	3.3	MVA	

4 Resilience driven use case

In this section, the methodology outlined in Deliverable 1.2 for assessing the resilience of electrical networks is applied to a specific distribution network. This approach, developed as part of the iPlug project, is summarized in Appendix B.1.

As described in the methodology, resilience assessment can be performed on any electrical network or a portion thereof. Resilience is not solely a technical, social, or economic matter; rather, a thorough analysis must incorporate multiple perspectives. An accurate resilience analysis must consider data from multiple sources and institutions, each providing information on events that may impact the system or the system's characteristics. The primary challenge in resilience analysis is that each institution or source presents data in a unique format and reports different types of information. Therefore, a critical stage is establishing effective communication and integration between these diverse data sets.

In this case study, the resilience of a part of an electrical distribution network owned and operated by Anell is analyzed. The methodology considers both the inherent vulnerabilities of the system and the potential hazards that may affect it. Hazards are external events that may impact the system, while vulnerabilities refer to its intrinsic characteristics.

A detailed characterization of the system is provided in Section 4.1. Sections 4.1.1 and 4.1.2 present a summary of the system's topology and the main incidents that affected it, while Section 4.1.3 develops a hazard database specific to the distribution network. The hazards considered in this analysis include both the technical specifications of the system and the geographical attributes of its location. Finally, Section 4.1.4 examines the system's vulnerabilities in relation to each identified hazard.

Following the system characterization, Section 4.2 will assess the baseline resilience of the network. In addition to evaluating the overall resilience, the analysis will identify which components and elements are most at risk. Based on these insights, Section 4.3 will explore how an MPC solution could enhance the system's resilience and mitigate the energy at risk.

4.1 System definition

This study considers a distribution network owned by Anell, a local DSO. The distribution network is in a rural area in Catalunya, Spain.

The distribution network presents two nominal voltages, a Medium Voltage level of 5 kV and a Low Voltage level of 400 V. The distribution network is connected to the main grid through a 20/5 kV substation in the northwestern regions. From this point, the 5 kV network supplies various MV to LV transformers, which, in turn, supply several Low Voltage loads. The 5 kV network manages the long distances between the consumption points. The low voltage distances are relatively low. In that context, from a resilience perspective, the Medium Voltage grid presents more challenges than the Low Voltage part. Thus, this analysis considers the aggregated consumption in each MV to LV transformer and the Medium Voltage infrastructure, i.e., the Low Voltage infrastructure is not evaluated in this case study.

This section presents the distribution network's main characteristics. First, Section 4.1.1 evaluates

the topology, the network’s technical characteristics and the consumption profiles. Second, Section 4.1.2 evaluates all incidents registered by Anell in the last decade to characterize the system’s strengths and weaknesses.

4.1.1 Electrical Network

Figure 52 shows the Medium Voltage distribution network considered in this case study. The image depicted three types of nodes in three different colors. First, nodes where more than two lines intersect (purple). Second, nodes that contain an overhead to underground power line conversions (yellow). Third, the end buses, where consumption loads might be located (orange). Not all end buses have power consumption, only those named in Figure 52 are currently registering electrical consumption.

Figure 52: MV Distribution Network - A case study. Types of buses. **Map scale:** 1 : 75 000.

Anell, as the DSO, provided the aggregated LV active and reactive consumption in the corresponding MV point. As the data considered contains information from multiple LV meters, having accurate and reliable data is a complex task. In that context, for most of the buses, accurate and reliable data from September 2023 to March 2024 is available. However, in some cases, there are some data gaps along the mentioned period. Figures 91a to 91y show the average daily profile for active and reactive power per season in each bus with consumption. From this analysis we can conclude:

1. Spring consumption curves are not available for any bus.

2. Although the DSO identified Bus 30203 and Bus 103924 as consumption points, the meters are not currently reporting data, i.e., no consumption registered in the considered period, Figures 91h and 91y.
3. Summer daily profiles only consider data from September 2023. As a result, the profile might not be representative of the whole season.
4. The available data is very limited for Bus 30025. Only partial data from September 2023 is registered, Figure 91g.
5. In Bus 31977 only data from January and February 2023 is available, i.e., only an average daily profile for winter is built, Figure 91m.
6. In Bus 33427 there is no available data for September and October 2023. Consequently, no average daily consumption curve is built for summer, Figure 91q.
7. In Bus 32486 a PV system is identified. The PV system is connected at some point in the LV distribution network. However, from the MV point, we can observe a consumption decrease during the solar hours. As the reactive power profile does not vary during solar hours, we can expect that the PF facility is only generating active power or with a power factor close to 1. It is worth mentioning that the PV system is currently supplying its surplus to the distribution network, Figure 91o.

In that context, we can conclude that the daily profiles obtained for winter and autumn are representative and accurate. However, the summer profiles should be carefully managed in all cases, as only one month is available. Given that, although the methodology and the hazard database allow a resilience analysis for all seasons, the authors consider focusing on autumn and winter due to the consumption profiles' accuracy for those seasons. It is worth mentioning that a whole year's evaluation would provide a deeper understanding of the system's risks and the MPC's potential for resilience increase. Thus, the possibilities and capacities of resilience analysis should encourage data collection.

Meanwhile, the DSO informed us about a planned PV facility that will be connected to the distribution network in the coming months. The planned PV facility would be connected at the LV level supplying its energy to the MV Bus 27200. The projected nominal power of the PV system is 100 kW_{AC}. As the PV system is not already built, no generation data is available. In that context, this work calculated the potential PV generation through the PVGIS database [5]. The PV generation calculations performed by PVGIS are described in [7].

The PV potential generation considers the solar radiation in the following point:

- **Latitude:** 41.823611°
- **Longitude:** 2.291667°

which, in Universal Transversal de Mercator, corresponds to:

- ETRS89 ZONE 31
- **Latitude:** 441175.62 m E
- **Longitude:** 4630434.75 m N

This analysis has considered the solar radiation data for the period 2005 - 2023. Additionally, the following characteristics are considered:

- **DC PV Power:** 125 kW_{DC}
- **Slope:** 15°
- **Azimuth:** 0°
- **Performance Ratio:** 79,24 %

The Performance Ratio is based on [8], where the authors evaluated the average performance ratio of a 50 MW PV facility located in Spain after 12 operation years.

Figure 53 shows the average generation PV profile per season. As the average performance ratio is considered, in the first operational years a higher generation should be expected in all seasons.

Figure 53: PV expected generation profile per season

Overhead and underground power lines are present in the system. The cabling material can be used to accurately identify the power line type. We have identified two cabling materials in the power lines information: aluminum and aluminum steel-reinforced. Aluminum steel-reinforced is mostly used in overhead power lines. These cables present good conductivity-to-weight and strength-to-weight ratios, [9]. In turn, aluminum power lines are typically underground. Surprisingly, no copper power lines are identified in the region. The lack of copper in the system is positive from a resilience perspective,

especially in light of the copper thefts that result from rising worldwide prices [10]. Figure 54 shows the overhead and underground power lines identified in the region.

Figure 54: MV Distribution Network - A case study. Types of power lines. **Map scale:** 1 : 75 000.

Additionally, for each power line, the DSO provided the resistance, the reactance, the capacitance, and the maximum admissible current. This data is essential to evaluate the characteristics of the system.

For a better understanding, an AC Optimal Power Flow is used to characterize the system state during a winter average day. The AC OPF is used because allows the modeling of reactive power and, consequently, voltage level variations. The analysis is performed in winter because a higher consumption than in autumn is registered. Consequently, the system will present a more critical operation condition. The Optimal Power Flow methodology, both DC and AC, is also used to determine the impact that each element, i.e., bus or power line, might have on the system. In this case, the AC OPF considers the system with all elements connected and without being affected by any disruptive event.

Figures 55 and 56 show the voltage level and Figure 57 the loading percentages vary along the distribution network on an average winter day. Considering both variables, we can conclude that the operation of the system is not critical. The voltage level is higher than 0,99 pu in all hours and the loading percentage never exceeds the 5,1 %. The results are reasonable considering the following:

1. The distribution network supplied residential consumers at the LV level. Consequently, the region's total consumption is relatively low.

2. There are no industrial consumers in the area.
3. The consumers are dispersed and the topology of the regions is steep. Consequently, an MV network is more convenient than an LV grid. However, if it were not for the system topology, a LV network would be sufficient for this demand.

Notwithstanding, some variations can be observed along the winter average day.

1. As the system is connected to the main grid through a single point, those buses farther to that point record lower nominal voltages.
2. The lowest nominal voltages are obtained from 11 am to 1 pm and from 5 pm to 8 pm in the western and eastern feeders, respectively.
3. Due to all consumption being supplied by a single point, a higher loading percentage is observed in the power lines that connect initial buses.
4. The lower loading percentages are observed from 10 am to 1 pm.

Figure 55: Per unit voltage level in each demand bus along winter day average.

Figure 56: Per unit voltage level in each bus along winter day average. **Map scale:** 1 : 250 000.

Figure 57: Loading percentage in each power line along winter day average. **Map scale:** 1 : 250 000.

4.1.2 Incidents Database

The local DSO recorded the incidents in the region since 2010. The database includes various types of incidents that have been affecting the system. Additionally, those incidents caused by maintenance tasks are also included. Over the last decade, the database has been improved. Nonetheless, it still does not include 100 % of events and the accuracy of the data varies from one event to the other, i.e., not the same information is recorded for all events.

In light of that, this work performs a deep database analysis to identify the main system’s vulnerabilities. In the period 2010 - 2024, 257 incidents were recorded in the system. All events are classified into 5 main categories as per Figure 58. 50 % of incidents are caused by the system’s failures, 26 % are due to planned discharges, 11 % are due to telecommunication issues, 9 % are faults in customers’ installation and 2 % are caused by a third party. Only 2 % of the events cannot be classified into one of the previous categories.

Figure 58: DSO Incidents Database classification. The percentages are calculated considering the 257 events recorded during the 2010 - 2024 period.

Planned discharges and system failures cause more than 2/3 of total incidents. Additionally, the DSO is directly responsible for these events. Thus, these two categories are investigated in more detail.

Figure 59 show that 30 % of the system’s failures are caused by failures in MV power lines. This percentage accounts for 38 incidents. For most of the incidents, detailed information is not available. However, considering the available detailed information, 5 incidents are caused by circuit breaker disconnection, which, in two cases, have been disconnected during storm events. A non-specific number of events recorded in MV power lines are related to the vegetation present in the area.

Figure 59: DSO Incidents Database classification. The percentages are calculated considering the 129 events classified in the category "Own failures" recorded during the 2010 - 2024 period.

The planned discharges include various maintenance tasks as per Figure 60. 18 % of planned discharges are related to pole replacement work. The DSO considers that wooden poles are a relevant weakness in the infrastructure due to the higher maintenance, lower resistance, and higher firing risk. Notwithstanding, after the wooden pole replacements included in the database, the remaining wooden poles in the system and their location are unknown.

Figure 60: DSO Incidents Database classification. The percentages are calculated considering the 68 events classified in the category "Planned discharges" recorded during the 2010 - 2024 period.

The third-party events are all related to machinery circulating or operating close to the system.

The hazard database is developed to include all hazard that might affect the system according to this section insights.

4.1.3 Hazards

Hazards are not universally objective; they are highly context-dependent and influenced by the specific characteristics of the system under consideration. For example, the theft of a particular material may pose a hazard in the context of high market prices, but only if that material is utilized within the system. Similarly, gusts of wind constitute a hazard when aerial components of the system are vulnerable to such conditions.

In this context, the hazard database is constructed based on the analysis of the electrical network presented in Section 4.1. The database includes six primary hazards: machinery, vegetation, storms, wind gusts, wildfires, and heatwaves. While vegetation and heatwaves are not direct hazards to an electrical network, they may contribute to system damage when combined with other factors. For instance, wind may cause direct damage to the system, or it may exacerbate the risk by interacting with vegetation.

Information regarding each hazard is sourced from specialized institutions, though the data provided often requires supplementation from additional literature. Figure 61 illustrates all the institutions and data sources that contributed to the construction of the hazard database. Six specific data sources are directly used to compile the hazard information along with the literature.

This section details the methodology for incorporating each hazard into the database. As various sources provide different types of information, all hazards are qualitatively classified based on their potential intensity and frequency of occurrence. Although the results are qualitative, they are grounded in objective data from multiple institutions. The analysis is conducted per each season of the year. The potential intensity considers how the hazard is given in the analyzed region, Table 21. The occurrence frequency evaluates how often the hazard is expected to be recorded, Table 22. These classifications are based on a thorough evaluation of each hazard.

INTENSITY SCORING FOR HAZARDS	
Very Low	Barely noticeable with minimal or no effect on the analyzed system.
Low	Low severity with minor potential impact on the analyzed system.
Moderate	Noticeable with limited interaction and effect on the analyzed system.
High	Severe with significant interaction affecting the analyzed system.
Very High	Critical with a substantial effect on the analyzed system.

Table 21: Categories to classify the hazard intensity in a certain region

PROBABILISTIC SCORING FOR HAZARDS	
Hardly ever	Very rare event.
Sometimes	Expected at least once in twenty years.
Often	Expected at least once in five years.
Usually	Expected at least once per year.

Table 22: Categories to classify the hazard intensity in a certain region

The qualitative analysis is utilized to numerically characterize each hazard, as outlined in Table 23, ensuring that all hazards are ultimately comparable.

Some hazards may occur simultaneously, compounding their effects. This section also examines the

HAZARD INDEX				
Level	Frequency			
	Hardly ever	Sometimes	Often	Usually
Very Low	0,05	0,10	0,15	0,20
Low	0,10	0,20	0,30	0,40
Moderate	0,15	0,30	0,45	0,60
High	0,20	0,40	0,60	0,80
Very High	0,25	0,5	0,75	1,00

Table 23: Hazard index

relationships between hazards, with each combination forming a new layer in the database. The hazard index of the primary layers is used to determine the hazard index of the combined hazards. Finally, the database contains 4 simple hazards and 6 composite hazards, resulting in 10 hazards overall.

Figure 61: Resilience analysis network.

The resilience of the network is continually evolving due to system modifications and changing boundary conditions. As a result, the hazard database must be regularly updated to incorporate emerging risks and ensure that existing hazards are accurately aligned with the network's current state.

Landcovers: machinery and vegetation hazard

Based on the analysis of recorded events in the distribution network examined in this study, two hazards related to land cover have been identified.

First, several incidents involve machinery either operating or moving through specific areas. The presence of such machinery is closely linked to land cover. In regions where tall machinery operates or

moves, such as on roads or in wooded areas, overhead power lines are often at risk of damage. Conversely, underground power lines in agricultural areas may be vulnerable to damage from farming activities. This analysis begins by identifying the different land uses and examining the machinery operating or moving through each area. Finally, the hazard for the system associated with each machinery type will be assessed. As a result, two layers will be generated: one related to machinery that could damage overhead power lines, and another associated with machinery that might cause damage to underground power lines. As two main types of machinery are explored—one performing aerial operations and the other operating underground—a single layer is insufficient. Notwithstanding, as described in Section 4.1.4, the analysis of power line vulnerabilities considers that each type of power line presents specific vulnerabilities to one hazard while being immune to the other.

Second, tree falls have caused significant damage to the network. Analyzing the vegetation in each region enables a more precise characterization of this hazard. Areas with dense vegetation and tall trees present a greater risk than those with sparse vegetation or open meadows.

The Institut Cartogràfic i Geològic de Catalunya (ICGC) has conducted a detailed study of the various land covers in the region [1]. Within the case study area, the ICGC identifies 24 distinct land cover types: seven types of forests, three types of crops, nine human-altered environments, and five types of meadows and other native non-forest vegetation.

Figure 62 illustrates the distribution of these land covers across the case study region.

Figure 62: Landcovers obtained from ICGC [1]. Map scale: 1 : 125 000.

Machinery

As mentioned, machinery working or circulating near to the network is identified as a relevant hazard for the system. In the case study region, the Grup de Recerca de Geobotànica i Cartografia de la Vegetació (GEOVEG), a research group from the University of Barcelona, conducted a detailed and accurate evaluation of the land covers present in the area during the period from 2015 to 2020 [11]. A notable aspect of the work performed by GEOVEG is the inclusion of precise fieldwork. This research is available online and can be downloaded as a shapefile. While the ICGC layer includes 24 landcovers, the GEOVEG work encompasses 116 different taxons. Although the GEOVEG work is more precise and accurate, it has lower resolution since land covers with an area smaller than 0,2 ha are reported as points instead of polygons. Thus, the information provided by GEOVEG is analyzed along with the land cover classification performed by the ICGC [12]. The following paragraphs detail the steps taken to develop the machinery hazard layers.

First, to evaluate the machinery accurately, the various categories included in the aforementioned

studies should be simplified. Second, each simplified category is thoroughly investigated. As a result, what types of work, how often, and when are performed are investigated. This analysis will explore what types of work are performed, how often, and when. The types of machinery used will also be evaluated to determine the hazard intensity. The frequency of each type of work will establish the frequency of the hazard. Finally, the timing of certain tasks will dictate the season in which the hazard is most probable.

Areas with small surface areas are not represented as polygons in the GEOVEG analysis; therefore, data from the ICGC should be considered. The regions detailed in Section 4.1.3 from the ICGC classification will be directly assessed from this layer. These surfaces are extracted from the GEOVEG layer to avoid double analysis. The nine regions identified will be classified into three simpler categories according to Section 4.1.3, which are deemed sufficient for evaluating the types of machinery involved.

REGION	TAG
Ponds	NA
Isolated Buildings in Rural Areas	NA
Reservoirs	NA
Lakes and Lagoons	NA
Bare Urban Soil	Industrial
Road Network	Industrial
Sports and Leisure Areas	Industrial
Industrial, Commercial, and/or Service Zones	Industrial
Green Areas	Green Area

Table 24: Simplified categories from ICGC layer

The total area considered in those 3 categories amounts to 49,70 according to Section 4.1.3.

TAG	Area (ha)
NA	14,02
industrial	16,38
green areas	19,30

Table 25: Area included in simplified categories from ICGC layer

Regarding the forest areas or regions with crops, the analysis provided by the ICGC is insufficient to determine the types and frequency of required work. In that context, the GEOVEG layer is used to characterize those regions. In the areas not included in the previous classification, GEOVEG identified 109 different land covers. Notably, 51,07 % of the area is occupied by montane evergreen oak forests on siliceous terrain, Catalan-Occitan. The 109 categories detailed by GEOVEG are classified into 22 simplified categories based on the predominant vegetation, along with an additional category that encompasses all areas that cannot be classified into the previous 22 categories. Table 26 summarizes the 23 simplified categories along with each total areas. The detailed classification is available in Appendix B.2.

TAG	AREA (ha)
evergreen oak	2 036,77
meadows	162,20
scrub	204,62
common beech	84,49
herbaceous crops	84,56
sessile oak	81,87
Populus or similar	29,71
thicket	29,75
others	20,80
pine	38,15
chestnut	6,86
aspen	4,70
ash	2,77
rocky areas	2,88
common hazel	1,81
grey willow	0,81
aquatic environment	0,50
tall fruit crops	0,24
cypress	0,12
elms	0,05
deciduous trees	0,03
cedar	0,02
platanus	0,01

Table 26: Area covered by different types of landcover based on GEOVEG work

In the end, 26 simplified categories are examined. Table 27 summarizes the evaluation performed. For each category the following variables are investigated: type of works performed, the most probable season of the year, the power lines that may be affected (underground / overhead), and frequency of the work.

	WORK	DESCRIPTION	SEASON	FREQ.	INFRASTR.	REF
industrial	maintenance tasks	trucks, excavators	all	annually	underground PL	
	circulation	high machinery and trucks	all	annually	overhead PL	
green areas	gardening	lawnmower	all	annually	overhead PL	
NA	interaction with the network not expected					
others	interaction with the network not expected					
evergreen oak	prune	very high machinery, trucks	spring	2 - 5 years	overhead PL	[13–15]
	cut down	high machinery, trees falling, trucks, tractors	spring	every 20 years	overhead PL	
aquatic environment	interaction with the network not expected					
chestnut thicket	specific works not required					[13, 14]
	specific works not required					[16]
deciduous trees	prune	very high machinery, trucks	winter	2 - 5 years	overhead PL	[16]
	cut down	high machinery, trees falling, trucks, tractors	winter	6 - 10 years	overhead PL	
common hazel	cut down	high machinery, trees falling, trucks, tractors	winter	6 - 10 years	overhead PL	[16]
cedar	clearing	tractors with plows	spring	2 - 5 years	underground PL	
	cut down	high machinery, trees falling, trucks, tractors	spring	15 years	overhead PL	[17]
tall fruit crops	till	tractors with plows	various	10 years	underground PL	
	prune	very high machinery, trucks	spring	1 - 2 years	overhead PL	[18, 19]
	cut down	high machinery, trees falling, trucks, tractors	various	15 years	overhead PL	
herbaceous crops	till	tractors with plows	various	annually	underground PL	[18]
common beech	gather	tractors, harvesters	various	annually	underground PL	
	cut down	high machinery, trees falling, trucks, tractors	winter	20 years	overhead PL	[14, 20]
ash	specific works not required					[14]
grey willow scrub	specific works not required					[14]
	interaction with the network not expected					
elms	specific works not required					[14]
pine	cut down	high machinery, trees falling, trucks, tractors	spring	6 - 10 years	overhead PL	[13, 14]
platanus	cut down	high machinery, trees falling, trucks, tractors	winter	20 years	overhead PL	[18]
populus or similar	clearing	tractors with plows	spring	1 - 2 years	underground PL	
	prune	very high machinery, trucks	spring	1 - 2 years	overhead PL	[21]
	cut down	high machinery, trees falling, trucks, tractors	spring	12 years	overhead PL	
meadows	interaction with the network not expected					
rocky areas	interaction with the network not expected					
sessile oak	cut down	high machinery, trees falling, trucks, tractors	winter	6 - 10 years	overhead PL	[13, 14]
aspen	interaction with the network not expected					[22]
cypress	clearing	tractors with plows	spring	1 - 2 years	underground PL	
	cut down	high machinery, trees falling, trucks, tractors	spring	15 years	overhead PL	[17]

Table 27: Machinery hazard evaluation based on landcover

Based on the information reported in Table 27, Tables 28 and 29 determine the machinery hazard for overhead and underground power lines for each season of the year. The hazard level is contingent upon the type of machinery used; consequently, it remains constant throughout all seasons.

	Intensity	Probabilistic Scoring			
	scoring	summer	autumn	winter	spring
industrial	Very Low	Sometimes	Sometimes	Sometimes	Sometimes
	Very High	Usually	Usually	Usually	Usually
green areas	Low	Usually	Usually	Usually	Usually
NA	Very Low	Hardly ever	Hardly ever	Hardly ever	Hardly ever
others	Very Low	Hardly ever	Hardly ever	Hardly ever	Hardly ever
evergreen oak	Very High	Hardly ever	Hardly ever	Hardly ever	Often
	Moderate	Hardly ever	Hardly ever	Hardly ever	Sometimes
aquatic environment	Very Low	Hardly ever	Hardly ever	Hardly ever	Hardly ever
chestnut	Very Low	Hardly ever	Hardly ever	Hardly ever	Hardly ever
thicket	Very Low	Hardly ever	Hardly ever	Hardly ever	Hardly ever
deciduous trees	Very High	Hardly ever	Hardly ever	Often	Hardly ever
	Moderate	Hardly ever	Hardly ever	Often	Hardly ever
common hazel	Moderate	Hardly ever	Hardly ever	Often	Hardly ever
cedar	Very Low	Hardly ever	Hardly ever	Hardly ever	Often
	Moderate	Hardly ever	Hardly ever	Hardly ever	Sometimes
tall fruit crops	Very Low	Often	Often	Often	Often
	Low	Hardly ever	Hardly ever	Hardly ever	Usually
	Low	Sometimes	Sometimes	Sometimes	Sometimes
herbaceous crops	Very Low	Usually	Usually	Usually	Usually
	Very Low	Usually	Usually	Usually	Usually
common beech	Moderate	Hardly ever	Hardly ever	Sometimes	Hardly ever
ash	Very Low	Hardly ever	Hardly ever	Hardly ever	Hardly ever
grey willow	Very Low	Hardly ever	Hardly ever	Hardly ever	Hardly ever
scrub	Very Low	Hardly ever	Hardly ever	Hardly ever	Hardly ever
elms	Very Low	Hardly ever	Hardly ever	Hardly ever	Hardly ever
pine	Moderate	Hardly ever	Hardly ever	Hardly ever	Often
platanus	Moderate	Hardly ever	Hardly ever	Sometimes	Hardly ever
populus or similar	Very Low	Hardly ever	Hardly ever	Hardly ever	Usually
	Very High	Hardly ever	Hardly ever	Hardly ever	Usually
	Moderate	Hardly ever	Hardly ever	Hardly ever	Sometimes
meadows	Very Low	Hardly ever	Hardly ever	Hardly ever	Hardly ever
rocky areas	Very Low	Hardly ever	Hardly ever	Hardly ever	Hardly ever
sessile oak	Moderate	Hardly ever	Hardly ever	Often	Hardly ever
aspen	Very Low	Hardly ever	Hardly ever	Hardly ever	Hardly ever
cypress	Very Low	Hardly ever	Hardly ever	Hardly ever	Usually
	Moderate	Hardly ever	Hardly ever	Hardly ever	Sometimes

Table 28: Intensity and Probabilistic Scoring Overhead power lines

	Intensity scoring	Probabilistic Scoring			
		summer	autumn	winter	spring
industrial	Very High	Sometimes	Sometimes	Sometimes	Sometimes
	Very Low	Usually	Usually	Usually	Usually
green areas	Very Low	Usually	Usually	Usually	Usually
NA	Very Low	Hardly ever	Hardly ever	Hardly ever	Hardly ever
others	Very Low	Hardly ever	Hardly ever	Hardly ever	Hardly ever
evergreen oak	Very Low	Hardly ever	Hardly ever	Hardly ever	Often
	Very Low	Hardly ever	Hardly ever	Hardly ever	Sometimes
aquatic environment	Very Low	Hardly ever	Hardly ever	Hardly ever	Hardly ever
chestnut	Very Low	Hardly ever	Hardly ever	Hardly ever	Hardly ever
thicket	Very Low	Hardly ever	Hardly ever	Hardly ever	Hardly ever
deciduous trees	Very Low	Hardly ever	Hardly ever	Often	Hardly ever
	Very Low	Hardly ever	Hardly ever	Often	Hardly ever
common hazel	Very Low	Hardly ever	Hardly ever	Often	Hardly ever
cedar	Moderate	Hardly ever	Hardly ever	Hardly ever	Often
	Very Low	Hardly ever	Hardly ever	Hardly ever	Sometimes
tall fruit crops	High	Often	Often	Often	Often
	Very Low	Hardly ever	Hardly ever	Hardly ever	Usually
herbaceous crops	Very Low	Sometimes	Sometimes	Sometimes	Sometimes
	High	Usually	Usually	Usually	Usually
	Low	Usually	Usually	Usually	Usually
common beech	Very Low	Hardly ever	Hardly ever	Sometimes	Hardly ever
ash	Very Low	Hardly ever	Hardly ever	Hardly ever	Hardly ever
grey willow	Very Low	Hardly ever	Hardly ever	Hardly ever	Hardly ever
scrub	Very Low	Hardly ever	Hardly ever	Hardly ever	Hardly ever
elms	Very Low	Hardly ever	Hardly ever	Hardly ever	Hardly ever
pine	Very Low	Hardly ever	Hardly ever	Hardly ever	Often
platanus	Very Low	Hardly ever	Hardly ever	Sometimes	Hardly ever
	Moderate	Hardly ever	Hardly ever	Hardly ever	Usually
populus or similar	Very Low	Hardly ever	Hardly ever	Hardly ever	Usually
	Very Low	Hardly ever	Hardly ever	Hardly ever	Sometimes
meadows	Very Low	Hardly ever	Hardly ever	Hardly ever	Hardly ever
rocky areas	Very Low	Hardly ever	Hardly ever	Hardly ever	Hardly ever
sessile oak	Very Low	Hardly ever	Hardly ever	Often	Hardly ever
aspen	Very Low	Hardly ever	Hardly ever	Hardly ever	Hardly ever
cypress	Moderate	Hardly ever	Hardly ever	Hardly ever	Usually
	Very Low	Hardly ever	Hardly ever	Hardly ever	Sometimes

Table 29: Intensity and Probabilistic Scoring Underground power lines

Figure 63 illustrates the machinery hazard for overhead and underground power lines across the different seasons of the year. Given that most of the region is occupied by forests, a higher hazard level is identified for overhead power lines compared to underground ones. For overhead power lines, spring emerges as the most critical season, as this is when the majority of work is conducted. Furthermore, the road traversing the region from northwest to southeast reports the highest hazard level for overhead power lines, as all machinery operating in the area must utilize this road.

Figure 63: Machinery hazard for overhead and underground power lines **a.1)** overhead - winter, **a.2)** hazard for overhead power lines in spring, **a.3)** overhead - summer, **a.4)** overhead - autumn, **b.1)** underground - winter, **b.2)** underground - spring, **b.3)** underground - summer, **b.4)** underground - autumn. **Area evaluated:** Case study region. **Map scale:** 1 : 200 000.

Vegetation

As mentioned, vegetation itself is not a hazard for an electrical network. However, its presence, particularly when combined with other hazards, can impact the system. In this context, this section investigates the vegetation hazard in the case study region.

Characterizing vegetation across large areas can be challenging. As shown in Figure 62, forests are the predominant land cover in the case study region. However, using a generalized forest classification to quantify hazards is insufficient. Forests are dynamic ecosystems that undergo constant changes, with their density varying significantly from one area to another. Additionally, these characteristics may evolve over time.

Given this context, monitoring vegetation has become increasingly important. The potential of aerial imagery for this purpose has attracted researchers' attention since the launch of the first Earth resources satellite in 1972 [23]. While aerial images can still be captured by satellites, several other technologies are now available, including aircraft, airborne platforms, and consumer drones. Aerial photos obtained through these technologies often contain errors due to perspective distortion or camera tilt. Orthophotos address these errors through an orthorectification process, ensuring that all data are spatially accurate and aligned with actual world features [24].

In the latter half of the 20th century, various methodologies were developed to analyze vegetation using aerial images or orthophotos. Researchers focused on identifying an optimal vegetation index. An ideal vegetation index should be "highly sensitive to vegetation, insensitive to soil background changes, and only slightly influenced by atmospheric path radiance." [25]. By 1995, over 40 vegetation indices were reported [23]. Vegetation indices rely on spectral reflectance produced by vegetation. Chlorophyll absorbs red light, while leaf cellular structures reflect near-infrared radiation. Consequently, combining red and near-infrared bands can provide valuable insights into a given area's photosynthetic activity, vegetation type, and density.

The first vegetation indices were introduced in 1972 by Pearson and Miller, including the "Ratio Vegetation Index" (RVI) and the "Vegetation Index Number" (VIN) [23]. A year later, the "Normalized Difference Vegetation Index" (NDVI) was proposed, which has since become one of the most widely used indices [26,27]. The NDVI is calculated as follows:

$$NDVI = \frac{NIR - R}{NIR + R} \quad (17)$$

It is important to note that aerial imagery is not always readily available. In such instances, consumer drones can be utilized to capture images; however, these typically only capture the visible spectrum. As a result, indices based on the RGB bands, such as VARI or GLI, may be more relevant in these scenarios [28].

For the current case study, the ICGC periodically conducts aerial surveys of the Catalan regions. The cameras used in these surveys capture the three visible color bands (red, green, and blue) in addition to the near-infrared band, with a resolution of 25 cm per pixel. The red and near-infrared channels are used

NVDI	Vegetation information
< 0	Water, artificial covers, etc.
0.0 - 0.2	Bare soil and/or dead vegetation
0.2 - 0.4	Sparse and/or weak vegetation
0.4 - 0.6	Abundant and/or vigorous vegetation
> 0.6	Very dense and very vigorous

Table 30: NVDI vegetation analysis proposed by [2]

to calculate the NDVI. The images are orthorectified using a 5-meter resolution Digital Elevation Model (DEM), and the final orthophoto is produced with a resolution of 1 meter. Each pixel in the orthophoto is assigned a value between -1 and 1, representing the NDVI. The ICGC has categorized NDVI values into five classes described in Table 30.

To evaluate the vegetation density across different segments of the network considered in this case study, the orthophoto must be polygonized. This process involves transforming the raster layer into a polygon layer, where each polygon provides information about the NDVI value. By doing so, the geometry of the network can be effectively compared to the geometry of the NDVI during the resilience analysis.

However, polygonized layers are significantly more complex than raster layers, making them more challenging to manage, especially over extensive areas. Therefore, the following steps will be undertaken to convert the raster containing NDVI information into a manageable polygonized layer:

1. The pixel resolution is reduced from 1x1 meters to 10x10 meters.
2. The NDVI raster, now with a 10-meter resolution, is polygonized. Each 10x10 meter pixel is converted into a 10x10 meter polygon, resulting in 293 113 features, i.e., 293 113 polygons. Evaluating intersections between these features and the network will require substantial computational time during resilience analysis.
3. Based on Table 30, an integer value from 0 to 4 is assigned to each polygon in a new attribute named “CLASS”.
4. All 10x10 meter polygons are dissolved by “CLASS” value. Non-adjacent geometries with the same CLASS value are also merged into the same polygon. This process reduces the layer to five polygons.

Despite this processing step reduces the resolution provided by the ICGC, the final resolution is considered sufficient, as the vegetation density is captured at 10x10 meters pixels resolution. Besides, the reduction in computational time offers significant advantages. Although vegetation might vary considerably from season to season, the data available from ICGC is updated annually. Therefore, this project assumes that the vegetation hazard remains constant throughout the year, as the vegetation density variation is relatively limited. However, it is essential to update the hazards layer annually to ensure an accurate resilience analysis.

In this case, both the intensity and probabilistic score are based on the vegetation density. Table 31 shows the qualitative categories assigned to each region.

	Intensity scoring	Probabilistic scoring - all seasons
Water, artificial covers, etc.	Very Low	Hardly ever
Bare soil and/or dead vegetation	Low	Hardly ever
Sparse and/or weak vegetation	Moderate	Sometimes
Abundant and/or vigorous vegetation	High	Often
Very dense and very vigorous	Very High	Often

Table 31: Intensity and Probabilistic Scoring Vegetation density

As a result, Figure 64 displays the vegetation hazard layer. In this case, only one season is shown, as all seasons are assumed to have the same hazard intensity and probability. The area is identified as having a moderate to high hazard level. As indicated in Figure 62, forests dominate the region, leading to dense vegetation throughout the landscape.

Figure 64: Vegetation Hazard index for all seasons. **Area evaluated:** Case study region. **Map scale:** 1 : 200 000.

Storms hazard

Based on the analysis of recorded events, storms caused some circuit breaker disconnections that resulted in supply interruption for some customers. In that context, electrical storms are considered a relevant hazard. According to [29], lightning monitoring provides information about the probability, location, and evolution of storms.

Meteorological institutions monitor lightning across various territories. The geospatial data related to lightning offers insights into where and when storms occur. Currently, both private and public institutions monitor their lightning geospatial data. The territory monitored varies depending on the source. Some

data providers evaluate and monitor lightning on a global scale, which results in lower resolution, while others focus on a national level or specific regions, achieving higher resolution data.

The accuracy of global providers may not suffice for evaluating lightning probabilities in the case study areas; thus, high-resolution data providers are considered. In Spain, the Agencia Estatal de Meteorología (AEMET) is a public meteorological institution responsible for monitoring lightning across the country [30]. Additionally, there are regional institutions that perform similar tasks. In the Catalan region, Meteocat oversees the monitoring of lightning both onshore and offshore [29].

Meteocat started the lighting monitorization in 2003 through the Atmospheric Electrical Discharge Detection Network (XDDE), which is an acronym derived from its designation in Catalan. This network, composed of four monitoring stations, measures the data in real-time, allowing for the determination of lightning locations with a precision ranging from 500 to 1 000 meters. For each lightning strike recorded, an uncertainty region is established based on the station’s location.

Currently, Meteocat provides a daily lightning data update through its Application Programming Interface (API). The API allows communication and data transfer from two different programs. In the case study, a Python code has been developed to download the data from the Meteocat API in a JSON format. Although the JSON data provided by Meteocat contains the coordinates of each lightning recorded, the data should be reorganized to meet the GeoJSON format. The GeoJSON format can be read by GIS softwares that map the data. Figure 65 shows the data reorganization to build a GeoJSON from the JSON file provided by Meteocat.

Figure 65: Meteocat JSON file obtained from Meteocat API and GeoJSON file created in Python to make information readable for GIS software

The Meteocat API received daily updates. However, only the 6-month data before the current day is available on the API. Additionally, the data available has not been processed due to these fast updates. As a result, the API might include lightning flashes with a peak current of 0 kA, or almost 0. Those lightning strikes are discarded during the processing stage.

The API service is a relevant tool for keeping the resilience analysis updated. However, this work considers that 1-year data is required as a starting point. In a 1-year dataset, the seasonal variation can be observed. In that context, Meteocat provided a 1-year of processed data. The data corresponds to the lightning strikes received during 2023, which ascend to 110 262.

As the current case study does not encompass the entire Catalan electrical network, an area of 60 000 hectares is established to evaluate the flashes of lightning that might affect the network. The area considered is illustrated in Figure 66. In the considered region, 2 690 lightning strikes have been recorded during the analyzed period.

Meteocat provides not only information about the location and timing of lightning strikes but also data on the peak current of each strike. A negative peak current indicates that the negative electrical charge is concentrated in the cloud, while the positive charge resides on the ground, causing electrons to flow from the cloud to the earth. Conversely, when a positive peak current is recorded, electrons move from the ground to the cloud, resulting from positive ions accumulating in the cloud's upper regions, which creates a more negatively charged earth. This phenomenon is less common; only 14 % of lightning strikes are classified as positive during the period from 2016 to 2021. However, positive lightning strikes are typically more critical, as they often occur during severe storm conditions and tend to follow a simpler path, with electrical loads having a single route [29].

In this context, the hazard is not solely determined by the probability of occurrence; the intensity of the lightning is also relevant. Various levels of protection against lightning are available for electrical networks. IEC 62305-1 establishes four Lightning Protection Levels (LPL) [31]. These levels include various categories, but this study focuses on the peak current threshold to evaluate how hazardous lightning could be for electrical networks, as higher peak currents necessitate a higher LPL. For the first positive impulse, LPL I protects up to 200 kA, LPL II up to 150 kA and LPL III and IV up to 100 kA. In turn, for the first negative impulse, LPL I protects up to -100 kA, LPL II up to -75 kA and LPL III and IV up to -50 kA.

Table 32 shows the distribution of recorded lightning strikes in the area over the year. Most of the lightning presents a relatively low pic current, and high-current lightning events are rare. Additionally, a seasonal pattern can be identified. Lightning strikes are much more probable during spring and summer than autumn and winter, when no flashes of lightning were recorded.

Category	Jan.	Feb.	Mar.	Apr.	May	Jun	Jul.	Aug.	Oct.	Nov.	Dec.
$I_{peak} \leq -100 \text{ kA}$	0	0	0	0	1	2	0	1	0	0	0
$-100 \text{ kA} < I_{peak} \leq -75 \text{ kA}$	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	0
$-75 \text{ kA} < I_{peak} \leq -50 \text{ kA}$	0	0	0	0	10	20	0	1	0	0	0
$-50 \text{ kA} < I_{peak} \leq -5 \text{ kA}$	0	0	0	19	1126	1206	26	129	1	0	0
$-5 \text{ kA} < I_{peak} \leq 5 \text{ kA}$	0	0	0	1	8	17	1	3	0	0	0
$5 \text{ kA} < I_{peak} \leq 100 \text{ kA}$	0	0	0	1	47	47	6	12	0	0	0
$100 \text{ kA} < I_{peak} \leq 150 \text{ kA}$	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	1	0	0	0
$150 \text{ kA} < I_{peak} \leq 200 \text{ kA}$	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
$200 \text{ kA} < I_{peak}$	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

Table 32: Lightning recorded per month and pic current.

Based on that, Table 33 qualitatively characterizes the flashes of lightning. As no lightning strikes were recorded during winter and autumn, a Hardly Every probabilistic score is considered for all peak currents in these seasons.

	Intensity	Probabilistic scoring			
	scoring	WINTER	SPRING	SUMMER	AUTUMN
$I_{peak} \leq -100 \text{ kA}$	Very High	Hardly ever	Often	Often	Hardly ever
$-100 \text{ kA} < I_{peak} \leq -75 \text{ kA}$	High	Hardly ever	Often	Often	Hardly ever
$-75 \text{ kA} < I_{peak} \leq -50 \text{ kA}$	Moderate	Hardly ever	Usually	Often	Hardly ever
$-50 \text{ kA} < I_{peak} \leq -5 \text{ kA}$	Low	Hardly ever	Usually	Usually	Hardly ever
$-5 \text{ kA} < I_{peak} \leq 5 \text{ kA}$	Very Low	Hardly ever	Usually	Sometimes	Hardly ever
$5 \text{ kA} < I_{peak} \leq 100 \text{ kA}$	Low	Hardly ever	Usually	Sometimes	Hardly ever
$100 \text{ kA} < I_{peak} \leq 150 \text{ kA}$	Moderate	Hardly ever	Sometimes	Often	Hardly ever
$150 \text{ kA} < I_{peak} \leq 200 \text{ kA}$	High	Hardly ever	Hardly ever	Hardly ever	Hardly ever
$200 \text{ kA} < I_{peak}$	Very High	Hardly ever	Hardly ever	Hardly ever	Hardly ever

Table 33: Intensity and Probabilistic Scoring Lighting

Considering previous evaluation, Figure 66 shows the hazard index per season in the case study region.

Figure 66: Lightning Hazard index **a)** winter, **b)** spring, **c)** summer, **d)** autumn. **Area evaluated:** Case study region. **Map scale:** 1 : 750 000.

Wildfire hazard

No incidents related to wildfires are identified in the data facilitated by the DSO of the region. However, land cover analysis reveals that forests dominate the area. Additionally, the vegetation analysis indicates the presence of dense vegetation within the case study region. Considering these factors and the potential for wildfires to cause significant damage to the electrical network and disrupt the electricity supply, an assessment of wildfire hazard is deemed essential in this context.

Wildfires are influenced by multiple variables and are challenging to predict in advance. Therefore, this analysis will utilize two data sources.

First, the hazard intensity is based on the vulnerability analysis performed by the Civil Protection Catalan Department. The institution assigns to each municipality a vulnerability level on a scale from 1 to 5. The vulnerability level is determined by analyzing vulnerable elements found within forested areas or within a 500-meter radius and considers factors such as population, the presence of hazardous materials, infrastructure, protected natural areas, and fuel models [32]. The analysis is provided in a shapefile. In addition to the vulnerability index, the file contains supplementary information, including the municipality code, total area, and total rural area of each municipality. As detailed in Table 34, the vulnerability level is assimilated to the hazard intensity, as it provides insight into the severity of

potential wildfires in each municipality.

INTENSITY SCORING FOR WILDFIRE HAZARD	
Very Low	Low vulnerability identified by regional civil protection department
Low	Moderate vulnerability identified by regional civil protection department
Moderate	Average vulnerability identified by regional civil protection department
High	High vulnerability identified by regional civil protection department
Very High	Very high vulnerability identified by regional civil protection department

Table 34: Intensity Scoring Wildfire

Second, the probabilistic score is established based on the historical data. This analysis considers wildfires that occurred in the Catalan region from 2011 to 2023. The statistical data is collected and provided by the Catalan Department of Agriculture, Livestock, Fishing and Food through the Dades Obertes application [33]. Although this data is presented in a spreadsheet format, it can be easily geolocated using the numerical code assigned to each municipality. From this dataset, the average forestal area burned per year and municipality is determined. In municipalities where a high percentage of the area is burned each year during the wildfire season, a greater probability of wildfire occurrence is inferred. Based on this analysis, Table 35 reports four probabilistic qualitative scores for wildfires.

PROBABILISTIC SCORING FOR WILDFIRE HAZARD	
Hardly ever	Average forest area burned during the season per year since 2011 $\leq 0,025$ %/yr
Sometimes	Average forest area burned during the season per year since 2011 $> 0,025$ %/yr and $\leq 2,5$ %/yr
Often	Average forest area burned during the season per year since 2011 $> 2,5$ %/yr and ≤ 5 %/yr
Usually	Average forest area burned during the season per year since 2011 > 5 %/yr

Table 35: Probability Scoring Wildfire

As a result, Figure 67 illustrates the hazard index in each season per municipality. The overall hazard index is relatively low throughout the territory since wildfires are infrequent events. However, a slight increase in the hazard index is observed in regions closer to the Mediterranean Sea during the spring and summer months. Notably, a municipality exhibits a very high hazard index during the summer.

It is important to highlight the medium hazard index reported in the northwest Catalan region. This area has been identified by the Civil Protection Department as highly vulnerable due to the characteristics of the forests present in the Pyrenees. Furthermore, significant wildfires have been identified in the region during winter months. For instance, the municipality of Alt Àneu experienced a wildfire in February 2011, while Naut Aran in January 2017 and 2019. Additionally, Pont de Suert recorded several during February and March 2012, 2014, 2016, 2017, and 2021 and during January 2017 and 2020 [33].

Figure 67: Wildfire Hazard a) winter, b) spring, c) summer, d) autumn. **Area evaluated:** Case study region. **Map scale:** 1 : 7 500k.

Wind hazard

Incidents related to wind gusts are not directly recorded in the DSO’s database. However, incidents involving fallen trees may be associated with wind presence, making it necessary to evaluate this hazard.

Typically, damages associated with wind occur during episodes of high wind gusts; regular winds should not impact infrastructure if it is properly operated and maintained. Thus, the focus of the wind hazard assessment is on evaluating wind gusts across Catalonia.

The Meteocat Annual Report provides data on the maximum wind gusts recorded at each meteorological station on a monthly basis. This study utilizes the 2023 Annual Report to perform the hazard intensity score [34]. The minimum geographical unit considered is the county, as not all municipalities have a meteorological station. The data provided by Metecoat is imported in a spreadsheet, where the highest wind gust per season and county during 2023 are identified. Based on this data, a hazard intensity is assigned to each county according to Table 36.

The Regional Civil Protection Institution provides a shapefile that includes the number of days per year when a wind gust superior to 20 m/s is recorded [35]. This information is utilized to determine the probabilistic score for wind gust occurrences in each municipality of Catalonia. Since the data is not segmented by season, the probabilistic score remains consistent across all seasons.

INTENSITY SCORING FOR WIND HAZARD	
Very Low	County maximum season wind gust ≤ 10 m/s
Low	County maximum season wind gust > 10 m/s and ≤ 20 m/s
Moderate	County maximum season wind gust > 20 m/s and ≤ 25 m/s
High	County maximum season wind gust > 25 m/s and ≤ 35 m/s
Very High	County maximum season wind gust > 35 m/s

Table 36: Intensity Scoring Wind

According to the different probabilistic categories defined in Table 22, most municipalities experience wind gusts as a common hazard, occurring at least once per year. Therefore, the category of "hardly ever" is not assigned to any municipality. Table 37 summarizes the assignment of the probability scores.

PROBABILISTIC SCORING FOR WIND HAZARD	
Hardly ever	-
Sometimes	Annual days with a wind gust of at least 20 m/s = 0
Often	Annual days with a wind gust of at least 20 m/s > 0 and ≤ 10
Usually	Annual days with a wind gust of at least 20 m/s > 10

Table 37: Probability Scoring Wind

The data provided by Meteocat can be easily combined with that from the Civil Protection Department using each county's code.

As a result, Figure 68 shows the wind hazard index obtained in each municipality. The index ranges from very low to very high across the territory, with most of the Catalan region showing a low to moderate hazard index. Notably, a high hazard index is identified in the case study region during the summer.

Figure 68: Wind Hazard **a)** winter, **b)** spring, **c)** summer, **d)** autumn. **Area evaluated:** Case study region. **Map scale:** 1 : 7 500k.

Heatwave hazard

Similar to the vegetation hazard, a heatwave does not directly impact an electrical network, as there is no physical interaction. However, heatwaves can indirectly affect the system when combined with other hazards. For example, the risk of wildfires significantly increases during a heatwave.

Meteocat defines a heatwave "maximum daily temperature above the 98th percentile for maximum temperature recorded during summer months" [36]. This percentile is calculated based on data from the preceding 10 years. However, since this data is not readily accessible, this project defines heatwave conditions as those in which the minimum daily temperature exceeds 20°C. This data is sourced from the Climate Change Scenarios Viewer developed in the context of the Spanish Plan Nacional de Adaptación al Cambio Climático (PNACC) and the project LIFE SHRA [37].

The viewer provides the information in shapefile format and includes various datasets and scenarios. These scenarios are based either on historical data or future projections. For this study, the data used is based on historical records from the period 1971–2000 [37].

The number of days with a minimum temperature exceeding 20°C is used to determine the probabilistic score of the hazard, as outlined in Table 38.

Regarding the intensity of the hazard, reliable and accurate information has not been obtained.

PROBABILISTIC SCORING FOR HEATWAVE HAZARD	
Hardly ever	Average days per season with a heatwave ≤ 5
Sometimes	Average days per season with a heatwave $> 5 \leq 20$
Often	Average days per season with a heatwave $> 20 \leq 35$
Usually	Average days per season with a heatwave > 35

Table 38: Probability Scoring Heatwave

Therefore, the hazard intensity is uniformly classified as **moderate** across all seasons.

Figure 69 shows heatwaves obtained for the case study region. During the winter and spring seasons, no days are expected to experience a heatwave. In autumn, a few areas exhibit a low hazard index. The highest hazard index is recorded in summer. Nevertheless, in the case study region, the hazard index remains very low across all seasons.

Figure 69: Wildfire Hazard a) winter, b) spring, c) summer, d) autumn. **Area evaluated:** Case study region. **Map scale:** 1 : 7 500k.

It is important to note that in the context of climate change, with rising temperatures, this layer should be carefully managed and updated in the coming years. Projections indicated in [37] anticipate an increase in the number of days experiencing heatwaves in future years.

Combined hazards

Some hazards can occur simultaneously, and their combination may affect both the likelihood of occurrence and the intensity of each hazard. The hazard index represents the probability of a specific hazard with a given intensity per season. In this context, hazard combinations are based on the relationship between two events. According to the methodology described in Appendix B.1, events can be classified as mutually exclusive, dependent, or independent. Since six simple hazards are defined, there are 15 possible combinations. Table 39 explores the relationships between these simple hazards.

According to iPlug's Deliverable 1.2., this project developed a Python-based QGIS plug-in to determine combined hazards. Through this tool, the hazard index of each combined hazard depends on the nature of the relationship between events. As described in the methodology, the hazard index for a combination of two independent events, A and B , is calculated as $P(A \cap B) = P(A) \cdot P(B)$, where P represents the hazard index. In contrast, when the combined hazard arises from two dependent events, the hazard index is calculated as $P(A \cap B) = P(A|B) \cdot P(B)$, where $P(A|B)$ refers to the probability of A given that B has occurred. For simplicity, the variation in the hazard index of event A , once B is given, is represented by applying a scaling factor. Only one combined hazard from dependent events is identified, namely wildfires combined with heatwaves. The available data on these two primary hazards is limited [38], as wildfires depend on multiple variables, and understanding their temperature dependence is a complex process. Nonetheless, [38] concludes that when a heatwave occurs, the likelihood of a wildfire increases.

By comparing the cumulative burnt areas shown in [39] with historical heatwave data from [40], significant wildfires can be identified during some heatwave periods. Since no precise quantitative value can be determined based on the available data, this study assumes a 10% increase in all seasons to reflect the findings reported in [38].

Figure 70 shows the hazard index for the combination of vegetation and wind. Other combined hazards resulted in very low to low hazard indices and can be consulted in Appendix B.3.

Nº	EVENT 1	EVENT 2	RELATION	Comment
1	vegetation	machinery	NO	The machinery hazard intrinsically considers vegetation density, as both are based on land cover evaluation.
2	vegetation	lightning	NO	The lightning hazard intrinsically considers vegetation density, as it accounts for recorded lightning strikes.
3	machinery	lightning	mutually exclusive	For safety reasons, machinery cannot operate during storm conditions.
4	vegetation	wind	independent	One hazard does not affect the probability of the other.
5	machinery	wind	mutually exclusive	For safety reasons, machinery cannot operate during windy conditions.
6	lightning	wind	independent	One hazard does not affect the probability of the other.
7	vegetation	wildfire	NO	The wildfire hazard intrinsically considers vegetation density.
8	machinery	wildfire	mutually exclusive	For safety reasons, machinery cannot operate during wildfire conditions.
9	lightning	wildfire	mutually exclusive	Wildfires and storms are not coincidental events.
10	wind	wildfire	independent	One hazard does not affect the probability of the other.
11	vegetation	heatwave	NO	As simple hazards do not affect the electrical network, neither does their coincidence.
12	machinery	heatwave	mutually exclusive	For health and safety reasons, machinery operators cannot work during heatwave conditions.
13	lightning	heatwave	mutually exclusive	During storm events, ambient temperatures tend to drop, making heatwaves unlikely.
14	wind	heatwave	NO	The events are independent. However, as heatwaves do not impact the system, the combination of wind and heatwave results in the wind hazard alone.
15	wildfire	heatwave	dependent	The wildfire hazard index increases when a heatwave occurs.

Table 39: Combined hazards resulting from two simple hazards.

Figure 70: Vegetation & Wind combined hazard **a)** winter, **b)** spring, **c)** summer, **d)** autumn. **Area evaluated:** Case study region. **Map scale:** 1 : 200 000.

Since the combination of vegetation and wind results in regions with a moderate hazard index, this combined hazard is evaluated alongside other primary hazards that could exacerbate system damage. Thus, vegetation and wind are examined in combination with lightning and wildfires. In both cases, the hazards are independent.

The obtained results show a very low to low hazard index for the two new layers. The resulting layers can be consulted in Appendix B.3.

In conclusion, the hazard database used for risk assessment and resilience analysis includes four primary hazards and six combined hazards, as described in Table 40.

Nº	HAZARDS DATABASE
1	machinery
2	lightning
3	wind
4	wildfire
5	vegetation + wind
6	lightning + wind
7	wildfire + wind
8	wildfire + heatwave
9	vegetation + wind + lightning
10	vegetation + wind + wildfire

Table 40: Hazard database

4.1.4 System's vulnerabilities

As mentioned in Appendix B.1, the proposed methodology distinguishes between hazards and vulnerabilities. If hazards were disruptive events that might affect the electrical network and out of its control, the vulnerabilities are the network's weaknesses. The vulnerability identification is based on the analysis reported in Section 4.1.2. The incidents database has already been considered in the hazard database.

This section is divided into three main parts. First, this work identifies the system's vulnerabilities. Second, it evaluates the global likelihood that the vulnerabilities affect an element given a specific hazard. Finally, we determine the potential impact each element might have on the system in case of failure.

Vulnerability identification

As hazards, the weaknesses or vulnerabilities of the system are not an objective. Economies, societies, and systems are constantly evolving. As a result, the system's resilience is not permanent. Conversely, it is a changing variable that should be constantly evaluated. A specific characteristic cannot be identified as good or bad, its evaluation should consider a context that cannot be avoided. Some system characteristics might be resilient to certain hazards and extremely weak to others. The convenience of a certain solution would depend on a global analysis. Consequently, a secure and reliable technology, material, or technical solution might be highly resilient in a specific context and notably vulnerable in another.

Considering all, this section evaluates the system vulnerabilities in the context of the hazards included in the database. Including the resilient perspective in electrical systems evaluation is challenging, as a large amount of accurate and reliable data is required. This notably diverges from previous concepts considered in the network's evaluation, such as efficiency or reliability. Currently, the available information is still limited, especially in distribution networks. Besides, the situation is still more complex in rural areas, where limited data is usually monitored due to the low number of customers and demand supplied. Most of the vulnerabilities identified in the system are related to its topology, i.e., buses and power line types. Table 41 summarizes the main vulnerabilities of the system.

Nº	VULNERABILITY
1	Absence of Lightning Protection System (LPS)
2	Underground node
3	Underground end node
4	Underground junction node
5	Overhead node
6	Overhead to underground conversion node
7	Overhead power lines
8	Underground power lines

Table 41: Network vulnerabilities

For a better understanding, below, we briefly describe each vulnerability.

1. Absence of Lightning Protection System (LPS)

The DSO provided the network's single-line diagram. From this information, the buses equipped with an LPS have been identified. Most of the buses are equipped or close to, at less than 10 meters, an LPS. However, some buses are identified as vulnerable in this sense. The LPS would be especially relevant during storm events.

2. Underground node

The network contains two types of underground nodes: end and junction ones. Those elements are vulnerable when certain hazards are given. In some cases, both are equally vulnerable or strong. However, some hazards might affect the system depending on the underground node type.

3. Underground end node

An underground end bus should be understood as a MV cabin that feeds a MV/LV transformer that supplies the LV grid.

4. Underground junction node

As for the underground junction buses, the network considered in this case study only considers points where two different types of cables are connected. As a result, points where two cables with the same characteristics are connected are not identified. In that context, the underground power lines might include additional junction points in their path. This would be considered in the likelihood evaluation.

5. Overhead node

Overhead nodes are poles used in the overhead power lines. Similarly, to underground junction nodes, the network considered does not include information about all poles installed in the system. Thus, the overhead power lines might contain some additional paths in their path. Most overhead nodes are junction nodes that connect more than two overhead power lines.

Additionally, information about the poles' material is not available. In the past, some maintenance tasks were planned in the network to replace wooden poles. However, there is no information about its current presence in the system.

It is worth mentioning that, according to the single-line diagram, additional poles do not include an LPS, as all LPS have been assigned to one of the considered nodes.

6. Overhead to underground conversion node

Overhead to underground conversion nodes are also poles. However, in this case, the poles connect, at least, one underground and one overhead power line.

Similarly to overhead nodes, there is no information about the material of those poles.

8. Overhead power lines and 9. Underground power lines

The power lines can be classified into two main groups: underground and overhead power lines. Both solutions are implemented in the analyzed network. Objectively, none of them is a good or bad solution. However, there is always one that is more convenient than the other. Until now, technical requirements and environmental or urban constraints defined the convenience of each solution. This work provides a resilience perspective.

Vulnerability likelihood

This section evaluated how the previously defined vulnerabilities might affect the system given each hazard included in the database.

First, Table 42 establishes 10 likelihood levels depending on how the weaknesses are mitigated.

LIKELIHOOD	LEVEL OF VULNERABILITY MITIGATION
0 %	There is no possibility of interaction between the element and the hazard. Failures are not expected to be caused by this hazard.
10 %	The element has a negligible likelihood of being affected by the hazard, though a protection mechanism is in place.
20 %	The element has a negligible likelihood of being affected by the hazard, and no protection mechanism is included.
30 %	The element has a moderate likelihood of being affected by the hazard. Protection is in place, along with redundancies to maintain operation in case of failure.
40 %	The element has a high likelihood of being affected by the hazard. Protection is in place, along with redundancies to maintain operation in case of failure.
50 %	The element has a moderate likelihood of being affected by the hazard. Protection is in place; however, there is no redundancy to maintain operation in case of failure.
60 %	The element has a high likelihood of being affected by the hazard. Protection is in place; however, there is no redundancy to maintain operation in case of failure.
70 %	The element has a high likelihood of being affected by the hazard. While it is not directly protected, nearby protection reduces its likelihood of being affected. No redundancies are in place to maintain operation in case of failure.
80 %	The element has a moderate likelihood of being affected by the hazard, but no protection or redundancy measures are in place.
90 %	The element has a high likelihood of being affected by the hazard, but no protection or redundancy measures are in place.

Table 42: Likelihood of each vulnerability depending on the mitigation level implemented for each hazard included in the database.

The vulnerability likelihood of each element should be identified for all hazards included in the database. An element protected against a hazard can be vulnerable once others are given, i.e., an LPS protects against lighting but does not have any effect during a strong wind event.

Considering all, Tables 43 to 53 provide the vulnerability likelihood to each element will be assigned depending on the level of protection identified. In each table, the level of protection will be established for a specific hazard included in the database. To avoid long tables, only the likelihood vulnerability assigned is detailed.

High-Access Machinery

The network's topology defines the vulnerability likelihood given the high-access machinery hazard. First, nodes are much less vulnerable than power lines given high-access machinery. Underground nodes are not expected to interact with this machinery. As for the overhead nodes, as they are physically poles, the machinery that can operate in this area is focused on keeping the area clear and free of vegetation. Therefore, work at a certain height is not expected near electric poles. Second, overhead power lines are the network's weakest point during the operation of this machinery.

Table 43 summarizes the vulnerability likelihood assigned to each type of element considering a high-access machinery hazard.

BUSES		
LH	ASSET TYPE	DESCRIPTION
10 %	Underground node	Located several centimeters below ground level, providing passive protection against high-access machinery.
20 %	Overhead to underground conversion node	Physically constructed as poles, which prevent machinery from operating close. However, the underground portion is potentially vulnerable.
POWER LINES		
LH	ASSET TYPE	DESCRIPTION
10 %	Underground power lines	Installed several centimeters below ground level, providing passive protection against high-access machinery.
90 %	Overhead power lines	Overhead power lines are particularly vulnerable during high-access machinery operations, as they may interfere directly with machinery.

Table 43: Likelihood assigned to asset type given High-Access Machinery hazard

Subsurface Machinery

Similarly to high-access machinery, the network's topology determines its vulnerability once the subsurface machinery hazard is given. In this case, those underground elements are considered especially weak during subsurface machinery operations. No information is available about the installation method used for those elements. Consequently, the most critical situation is considered. The use of concrete trenches for power lines or concrete manholes for underground nodes might significantly reduce this vulnerability likelihood. However, the environmental impact of those materials is notably larger.

Table 44 summarizes the vulnerability likelihood assigned to each type of element considering a subsurface machinery hazard.

BUSES		
LH	ASSET TYPE	DESCRIPTION
20 %	Overhead and Overhead to underground conversion nodes	These nodes are physically poles, reducing the risk of close machinery operations. The underground part is potentially vulnerable to subsurface machinery impacts.
90 %	Underground node	Some installations (e.g., concrete manholes) may reduce vulnerability, but lacking specific information, the most critical likelihood is assumed.
POWER LINES		
LH	ASSET TYPE	DESCRIPTION
20 %	Overhead power lines	Overhead power lines are not affected by subsurface machinery due to their elevated position.
90 %	Underground power lines	Certain installation methods, like concrete cable trenches, may reduce vulnerability to subsurface machinery. However, without specific information, the highest vulnerability likelihood is assumed.

Table 44: Likelihood assigned to asset type given Subsurface Machinery hazard

Lightning

As mentioned, the absence of an LPS is considered a relevant vulnerability. This vulnerability is relevant during storm events, alone or combined with other disruptive events. However, not all unprotected elements present the same vulnerability likelihood. Underground elements, i.e., power lines or nodes are not expected to be affected by a lightning strike. Additionally, there is always an LPS between overhead and underground elements that would prevent a fault from affecting the underground infrastructure.

Table 45 summarizes the vulnerability likelihood assigned to each type of element considering a lightning strike hazard.

BUSES		
LH	ASSET TYPE	DESCRIPTION
10 %	Underground node with LPS	Nodes located within 10 meters of an LPS are considered equally protected from lightning strikes.
20 %	Underground node without LPS	Nodes that are not equipped with or located close to an LPS.
60 %	Overhead and Overhead to underground conversion node with LPS	Only overhead nodes that include an LPS.
70 %	Overhead and Overhead to underground conversion node close to an LPS	Nodes located within 10 meters of an LPS. The protection system helps mitigate the vulnerability to lightning strikes.
90 %	Overhead and Overhead to underground conversion nodes without LPS	Nodes lacking LPS protection and located far from an LPS, which increases vulnerability to lightning damage.
LH	ASSET TYPE	DESCRIPTION
10 %	Underground power lines with LPS	All underground power lines are connected to a Lightning Protection System (LPS) at their endpoints, minimizing the risk from lightning strikes.
70 %	Overhead power lines with LPS	Although connected to an LPS at endpoints, overhead power lines remain more vulnerable to lightning than underground lines, especially during storm events.

Table 45: Likelihood assigned to asset type given Lightning hazard

Wind

The wind hazard is not expected to interact with the underground infrastructure. However, this is a critical hazard for overhead elements. Both for buses and power lines a high vulnerability likelihood is assigned.

Overhead and overhead to underground conversion nodes, in both cases, present a high vulnerability, due to the poles being the weakest point during high wind speeds.

Overhead power lines might include additional poles for cabling support along their path. High wind speed may have a significant effect on cabling, though the presence of poles mostly affects the vulnerability likelihood.

Table 46 summarizes the vulnerability likelihood assigned to each type of element considering a high wind speed hazard.

BUSES		
LH	ASSET TYPE	DESCRIPTION
10 %	Underground node	Not affected by wind hazards due to its below-ground installation.
90 %	Overhead and Overhead to underground conversion node	These nodes, as poles, are highly vulnerable to damage during strong wind events due to their exposed position.
POWER LINES		
LH	ASSET TYPE	DESCRIPTION
10 %	Underground power lines	These lines are unaffected by wind hazards due to their underground positioning.
90 %	Overhead power lines	Overhead lines are designed to withstand high wind speeds, but the poles supporting them are vulnerable to wind-induced damage. Trees falling on the lines may further compromise the infrastructure.

Table 46: Likelihood assigned to asset type given Wind hazard

Wildfire

Again, overhead elements are more vulnerable during wildfire events. Underground infrastructure is not expected to interact with wildfires as its installations become a passive protection system. However, underground junction nodes, where two cables are interconnected, are expected to be slightly vulnerable due to a temperature increase. Contrary, the overhead elements are significantly more vulnerable.

Wooden poles would be especially critical during wildfires. However, no information is available about its presence in the system and potential location. In that context, this work assumes that some overhead and overhead to underground conversion nodes might be wooden poles. Similarly, we consider that overhead power lines might include wooden poles along their paths.

Table 47 summarizes the vulnerability likelihood assigned to each type of element considering a wildfire hazard.

BUSES		
LH	ASSET TYPE	DESCRIPTION
10 %	Underground end node	These elements are not expected to be affected by wildfire damage due to their underground positioning.
20 %	Underground junction node	Points where two underground cables are connected are expected to be vulnerable during high temperatures.
90 %	Overhead and Overhead to underground conversion node	Wooden poles are particularly vulnerable to fire. Since it is uncertain if wooden poles are present throughout the network, the highest vulnerability likelihood is assumed.
POWER LINES		
LH	ASSET TYPE	DESCRIPTION
10 %	Underground power lines	These lines are not expected to be affected by wildfire due to their underground installation.
90 %	Overhead power lines	The use of wooden poles increases vulnerability to wildfire. Since the presence of wooden poles cannot be ruled out across the network, the highest vulnerability likelihood is assumed.

Table 47: Likelihood assigned to asset type given Wildfire hazard

Combined hazards

Tables 48 to 53 summarizes the vulnerability likelihood considered in all combined events. Table 48 for the presence of dense vegetation and high wind speeds. Table 49 considers the coexistence of lightning strikes and high wind speeds. Table 50 evaluates the system when a wildfire is given in a high wind speed context. Table 51 analyzes the combination of heatwaves and wildfires. Table 52 report a 3 events combination. Table 52 studies the system’s vulnerabilities when dense vegetation, high wind speeds, and lightning strikes simultaneously occur. Finally, Table 53 investigates the dense vegetation, high wind speeds, and wildfires combination.

In all cases, the vulnerability likelihood considers the vulnerabilities detailed in the simple hazards. In combined hazards that include heatwaves and dense vegetation, which have not been considered simple hazards, we evaluate if additional vulnerabilities in the system might emerge when those events are combined with others.

BUSES		
LH	ASSET TYPE	DESCRIPTION
10 %	Underground node	Not affected by wind and vegetation hazards due to its underground location.
90 %	Overhead and Overhead to underground conversion node	These nodes, especially poles, are very weak during strong wind events. The presence of vegetation may increase the damage to the infrastructure.
POWER LINES		
LH	ASSET TYPE	DESCRIPTION
10 %	Underground power lines	Underground power lines are not impacted by wind and vegetation hazards due to their below-ground installation.
90 %	Overhead power lines	Overhead power lines are highly vulnerable to high wind speeds, especially in areas with vegetation, which increases the likelihood of tree-fall damage on the infrastructure.

Table 48: Likelihood assigned to asset type given Vegetation and Wind hazard

BUSES		
LH	ASSET TYPE	DESCRIPTION
10 %	Underground node with LPS or close to it	Nodes located within 10 meters of an LPS are assumed protected against lightning. Wind does not typically affect these nodes due to their underground placement.
20 %	Underground node without LPS	Underground nodes that are not equipped with or located close to an LPS.
90 %	Overhead and Overhead to underground conversion node	While some overhead nodes include an LPS, this protection does not mitigate vulnerability during high wind speed events.
POWER LINES		
LH	ASSET TYPE	DESCRIPTION
10 %	Underground power lines with LPS	Equipped with an LPS at endpoints, underground lines are protected from lightning damage and unaffected by wind due to their below-ground location.
90 %	Overhead power lines	Although these lines are connected to an LPS at endpoints, they remain vulnerable to high wind speeds and potential lightning strikes.

Table 49: Likelihood assigned to asset type given Lightning and Wind hazard

BUSES		
LH	ASSET TYPE	DESCRIPTION
10 %	Underground end node	These nodes are not expected to be affected by combined wildfire and wind damage due to their underground installation.
20 %	Underground junction node	Points where two underground cables are connected are expected to be vulnerable during high temperatures.
90 %	Overhead and Overhead to underground conversion node	Wooden poles are highly susceptible to wildfire damage and can also suffer from structural weakness during high wind speeds. Since it is uncertain if wooden poles are present throughout the network, the highest vulnerability likelihood is assumed.
POWER LINES		
LH	ASSET TYPE	DESCRIPTION
10 %	Underground power lines	These elements are not expected to be affected by wildfire or wind due to their underground position.
90 %	Overhead power lines	Wooden poles are particularly weak against wildfire and high wind events. Since it is uncertain if all poles are fire-resistant, the highest vulnerability likelihood is considered.

Table 50: Likelihood assigned to asset type given Wildfire and Wind hazard

BUSES		
LH	ASSET TYPE	DESCRIPTION
10 %	Underground end node	These elements are not expected to be affected by wildfire or heat-wave damage due to their below-ground position.
20 %	Underground junction node	High temperatures may impact connections at junction nodes, potentially leading to damage.
90 %	Overhead and Overhead to underground conversion node	Wooden poles are particularly vulnerable to wildfire in high-temperature conditions. The highest vulnerability likelihood is considered.
POWER LINES		
LH	ASSET TYPE	DESCRIPTION
10 %	Underground power lines	These elements are not expected to be affected by wildfire or heat-wave hazards due to their underground position.
90 %	Overhead power lines	Overhead lines with wooden poles are highly susceptible to wildfire, especially in high-temperature conditions. The highest vulnerability likelihood is assumed given the potential for fire spread.

Table 51: Likelihood assigned to asset type given Wildfire and Heatwave hazard

BUSES		
LH	ASSET TYPE	DESCRIPTION
10 %	Underground node with LPS	Nodes located within 10 meters of an LPS, providing protection against lightning. Wind and vegetation hazards do not affect these nodes significantly due to their underground placement.
20 %	Underground node without LPS	Nodes lacking LPS equipment or proximity, increasing vulnerability to lightning.
90 %	Overhead and Overhead to underground conversion node	Wooden poles are vulnerable to damage from both strong winds and lightning in vegetated areas. The highest vulnerability likelihood is applied due to these compounded risks.
POWER LINES		
LH	ASSET TYPE	DESCRIPTION
10 %	Underground power lines	Protected by an LPS at endpoints and unaffected by wind and vegetation hazards due to their underground placement.
90 %	Overhead power lines	Vulnerable to damage from lightning and strong winds in vegetated areas. Wooden poles especially increase the vulnerability, so the highest vulnerability likelihood is assumed.

Table 52: Likelihood assigned to asset type given Vegetation, Wind and Lightning hazard

BUSES		
LH	ASSET TYPE	DESCRIPTION
10 %	Underground end node	These elements are not expected to be affected by vegetation, wind, or wildfire damage due to their below-ground location.
20 %	Underground junction node	High temperatures can impact connections at junction nodes, increasing the likelihood of damage.
90 %	Overhead and Overhead to underground conversion node	Wooden poles are especially vulnerable to wildfire and strong wind events, especially in areas with vegetation. Given the risk profile, the highest vulnerability likelihood is applied.
POWER LINES		
LH	ASSET TYPE	DESCRIPTION
10 %	Underground power lines	Not expected to be impacted by vegetation, wind, or wildfire due to their below-ground position.
90 %	Overhead power lines	Wooden poles are highly susceptible to wildfire and strong winds, especially in areas with dense vegetation. Without confirmed fire resistance, the highest vulnerability likelihood is assumed.

Table 53: Likelihood assigned to asset type given Vegetation, Wind and Wildfire hazard

Finally, Figures 71 and 72 provide the element's vulnerability likelihood established in previous tables for each simple and composed hazard, respectively.

Figure 71: Global vulnerability likelihood considered given each simple hazard: **a)** lightning, **b)** high-access machinery, **c)** subsurface machinery, **d)** wind gusts, **e)** wildfire **Area evaluated:** Case study region. **Map scale:** 1 : 150 000, Detail A: 1 : 750, Detail B: 1 : 50, Detail C: 1 : 150.

Figure 72: Global vulnerability likelihood considered given each composed hazard: **a)** vegetation + wind, **b)** lightning + wind, **c)** wildfire + wind, **d)** wildfire + heatwave, **e)** vegetation + wind + lightning, **f)** vegetation + wind + wildfire **Area evaluated:** Case study region. **Map scale:** 1 : 150 000, Detail A: 1 : 50, Detail B: 1 : 150.

Vulnerability impact

The consequences of losing each element of the system are determined through an Optimal Power Flow (OPF) as described in Appendix B.1. The impact of an element i is obtained through the difference between the energy supplied when all elements are connected and the energy supplied when element i is not in operation.

According to iPlug's Deliverable 1.2., this work developed a Python-based QGIS plug-in to determine the impact of each element present in an electrical network from GIS layers, i.e., one for buses and one for layers. Since previous work, this case study includes the following improvements:

1. **Season selection.** As the hazards database includes the probability of each hazard per season, the impact can be determined for a specific season of the year.
2. **Active and Reactive Power.**
 - (a) **Active Power:** The previous version included 3 different hourly profiles (residential, commercial and industrial) which determined the hourly consumption considering an instantaneous active power demand specified by the user. Now, the user can introduce the actual active power consumption profiles per hour.
 - (b) **Reactive Power:** The previous version determined the reactive power consumed by each load based on a constant power factor. Now, the user can introduce the actual reactive power both in instantaneous and hourly analysis. In the hourly analysis, hourly reactive power profile can be introduced.
3. **Power lines.** In the previous version the user should select the power lines among some standard types. In this version, the user can indicate the technical characteristics of each line/segment and the power line/segment is considered accordingly.

For further information about Python-based QGIS plug-in updates check Appendix B.4.

For buses, Table 54 reports the input parameters considered.

Field Name	Information included	Value
Name*	Bus Code	as per DSO
X	Longitude coordinate	as per DSO
Y	Latitude coordinate	as per DSO
SET	SET Name	as per DSO
Voltage_kV*	Voltage level	as per DSO
Vertex_Ty	End node / overhead to underground conversion / more than two lines	As per Figure 52
GRID*	1 for buses connected to main grid 0 for buses NOT connected to main grid	1 in Bus 27154 0 in all other buses
Type_GEN*	PV - bus with a generator capable to regulate the terminal voltage PQ - bus with a generator without voltage control NO_gen - bus without generators	PQ in Bus 27200 NO_gen in all other buses
PL_Av_Au*	Autumn average instantaneous active power	Determined through average consumption curves Figures 91a to 91y
PL_Av_Wi*	Winter average instantaneous active power	
PL_Av_Sp*	Spring average instantaneous active power	
PL_Av_Su*	Summer average instantaneous active power	
QL_Av_Au*	Autumn average instantaneous reactive power	
QL_Av_Wi*	Winter average instantaneous reactive power	
QL_Av_Sp*	Spring average instantaneous reactive power	
QL_Av_Su*	Summer average instantaneous reactive power	
{PL_00_Au,... PL_24_Au}**	Autumn average instantaneous active power	
{PL_00_Wi,... PL_24_Wi}**	Winter average instantaneous active power	
{PL_00_Sp,... PL_24_Sp}**	Spring average instantaneous active power	Profiles shows in average consumption curves
{PL_00_Su,... PL_24_Su}**	Summer average instantaneous active power	Figures 91a to 91y
{QL_00_Au,... QL_24_Au}**	Autumn average instantaneous reactive power	
{QL_00_Wi,... QL_24_Wi}**	Winter average instantaneous reactive power	
{QL_00_Sp,... QL_24_Sp}**	Spring average instantaneous reactive power	
{QL_00_Su,... QL_24_Su}**	Summer average instantaneous reactive power	

Table 54: Buses input parameters considered to determine the impact of each element. * Parameters considered in the OPF to determine the impact. Those parameters must be introduced in all impact calculations. ** Parameters considered in the hourly OPF to determine the impact. Those parameters must be introduced in all hourly impact calculations. Other parameters are included as additional information.

For power lines, Table 55 reports the input parameters considered.

Field Name	Information included	Value
Line_Name*	Line code	assigned in the case study
r_ohm_km*	resistance of the line in Ohm per km	as per DSO
x_ohm_km*	inductance of the line in Ohm per km	as per DSO
c_nf_km*	capacitance of the line in nano Fard	as per DSO
i_max_kA*	maximal thermal current in kA	as per DSO
PARALLEL*	number of parallel circuits	as per DSO
TYPE	OH - overhead power lines	as per DSO
	UG - underground power lines	Figure 54
Material	conductor's material	as per
	aluminium or steel plus aluminium	DSO

Table 55: Power lines input parameters considered to determine the impact of each element. * Parameters considered in the OPF to determine the impact. Those parameters must be introduced in all impact calculations. ** Parameters considered in the hourly OPF to determine the impact. Those parameters must be introduced in all hourly impact calculations. Other parameters are included as additional information.

As described in Section 4.1.1, the consumption data for summer and spring is not available or not accurate enough to be considered as a case study. Thus, considering only autumn and winter consumption profiles, the following impact calculation simulations can be performed through the Python-based QGIS plug-in:

- | | |
|--|--|
| <p>1. WINTER:</p> <p>1.1. DC OPF:</p> <p> 1.1.1. Instantaneous</p> <p> 1.1.2. Hourly</p> <p>1.2. AC OPF:</p> <p> 1.2.1. Instantaneous</p> <p> 1.2.2. Hourly</p> | <p>2. AUTUMN:</p> <p>2.1. DC OPF:</p> <p> 2.1.1. Instantaneous</p> <p> 2.1.2. Hourly</p> <p>2.2. AC OPF:</p> <p> 2.2.1. Instantaneous</p> <p> 2.2.2. Hourly</p> |
|--|--|

The Hourly AC OPF is the most accurate analysis. First, while the DC OPF only considers the active power, the AC OPF considers reactive power and, consequently, the voltage level constraints. Second, the hourly AC OPF could provide more accurate information about each element's impact on the system. This impact quantification approach would be especially relevant in those cases where the required time to recover the system after a failure caused by a certain risk is addressed. The current case study does not address the recovery time. Thus, hourly and instantaneous analysis should end up with similar results in terms of resilience. Currently, the Python-based QGIS plug-in allows simulation up to 24 hours. The time AC OPF requires is larger than that required by DC OPF due to additional constraints. Besides, the computational times increase exponentially when extra hours are included.

This work has determined the impact of each element under all previously defined scenarios. To compare the accuracy of the simulations, Table 56 compares the impact obtained for BUS 27154, which is the one connected to the main grid and, consequently, the one that reports the major impact. In all

cases, the impact is quantified in kWh per day. As the instantaneous analysis considers the daily average active and reactive power, the impact in kWh per day is obtained by multiplying the instantaneous impact by 24. Additionally, Table 56 shows the computational time required for the impact evaluation.

WINTER	Impact (kWh/day)	Time (s)
Instantaneous DC OPF	1414,008	6,57
Hourly DC OPF	1413,970	129,10
Instantaneous AC OPF	1414,008	47,51
Hourly AC OPF	1413,970	1165,61
AUTUMN	Impact (kWh/day)	Time (s)
Instantaneous DC OPF	1363,584	6,64
Hourly DC OPF	1363,518	129,90
Instantaneous AC OPF	1363,584	46,37
Hourly AC OPF	1363,518	1177,99

Table 56: Daily energy impact (kWh/day) for Bus 27154, calculated using both DC and AC Optimal Power Flow (OPF) methods. For each OPF, two analyses were performed. First, an instantaneous analysis using average values from the 24-hour load profile, Second, an hourly analysis considering de 24-hour load profile.

Due to the non-criticality of the system described in Section 4.1.1, the impact obtained through DC and AC OPF is the same. The computational time notably increases when the AC OPF is performed. An AC OPF takes 7 - 9 times more computational time. Regarding the consumption data, a slight difference is observed between the hourly and the instantaneous simulations, making the instantaneous analysis less accurate. Nonetheless, the instantaneous analysis requires much less time. The instantaneous AC OPF takes between 45 and 50 seconds while the hourly AC OPF requires almost 20 minutes.

This work considers the same element's impact for all hazards included in the hazard database, i.e., the recovery time required after a failure caused by a specific hazard is not evaluated. Consequently, assuming the results of the 24-hour OPF as each element's impact would imply that all hazards cause a one complete day outage in the system, which would be a very pessimistic consideration. Thus, although this work investigates the impact of each element through the different methods implemented in the Python-based QGIS plug-in, the impact analysis considers the ones obtained in the Instantaneous AC OPF. Figures 73 and 74 show the impact per day of each element in winter and autumn, respectively.

Figure 73: Network’s impact evaluation determined through an Hourly AC OPF considering winter power demand. **Map scale:** 1 : 100 000, Detail A: 1 : 250, Detail B: 1 : 10.

Figure 74: Network’s impact evaluation determined through an Hourly AC OPF considering autumn average power demand. **Map scale:** 1 : 100 000, **Detail A:** 1 : 250, **Detail B:** 1 : 10.

First, it is relevant to note that autumn and winter report similar results as the average power supplied in each node does not significantly differ from one season to the other.

Those elements close to the main grid’s connection point present a higher impact due to its disconnection resulting in the incapability to supply the system. Details A and B provide more detailed information about the network’s topology in this critical region. The Bus 27200 is limited as its disconnection only affects downstream connected LV loads.

Among the two feeders identified in the network, the northeastern one presents a higher criticality as it supplies most of the total demand.

4.2 Base resilience analysis

After defining the hazard database and characterizing the system vulnerabilities, this work addresses the resilience analysis.

The resilience analysis is based on a risk assessment evaluation, as described in Appendix B.1. The risk assessment evaluates the hazard index, the vulnerability likelihood, and the vulnerability impact. As a result, it determines the amount of energy at risk at each element, i.e., bus or power line.

As mentioned in iPlug’s Deliverable 1.2., this work developed a Python-based QGIS plug-in to perform the resilience evaluation based on the GIS layers obtained from previous evaluations, i.e., hazards and vulnerabilities.

The evaluation returns two main results. On one hand, the amount of power / energy at risk in each element. On the other, a global resilience index.

Regarding the first, Figures 75 and 76 show the amount of power at risk in each element in a winter and autumn average day, respectively. As mentioned, this work provides a power analysis, instead of energy, because the recovery time has not been investigated. Detail A shows, in both Figures, the risk assessment for Bus 29278, which presents the highest demand.

It is relevant to note that the amount of power considered at risk might exceed the element’s impact. For each hazard, the impact considered is obtained in Section 4.1.4. Then, weighting is achieved by multiplying the hazard index and vulnerability likelihood. However, each element can be impacted by multiple hazards. Consequently, the maximum power at risk for a given element may exceed the power it supplies. The maximum risk depends on the number of hazards included in the database. Those elements that present a risk above the total demand should be prioritized in the introduction of mitigation actions. Those elements would likely present a high impact, significant weaknesses, and a high probability of being affected by hazards.

Figure 75: Network’s risk assessment for an average winter hour. **Map scale:** 1 : 100 000, **Detail A:** 1 : 75.

Figure 76: Network’s risk assessment for an average autumn hour. **Map scale:** 1 : 100 000, **Detail A:** 1 : 75.

From this first analysis, we can draw the following main conclusions. First, the points close to the main grid tend to be more critical during winter and autumn. These points present a high risk due to impacting the supply of the whole demand. Second, a higher risk is observed during winter. The higher risk is caused mainly by wind speed hazard, which present a Low level during autumn and a Moderate one in winter. Furthermore, all composed hazards that account for high wind speed are also increased. Third, overhead power lines present a higher energy risk than underground cables.

According to iPlug’s Deliverable 1.2., the resilience index can be determined as follows (see ??):

$$\mathcal{R} = 1 - \frac{R_T}{I_T} \quad (18)$$

where R_T is the total energy at risk in the system and I_T the sum of partial impacts.

The previously defined index showed some limitations during the current case study. In that context, the authors decided to improve the previous resilience index to mitigate its weaknesses.

First, the previous index relies on the element’s impact on the system. However, each element’s impact varies when some mitigation actions are introduced in the network. In that context, I_T is redefined as:

$$I_T = \sum_x \sum_t p_{load-x,t} \cdot (f + w) \quad (19)$$

where $\sum_x \sum_t p_{load-x,t}$ is the total system's demand obtained from the power supplied, $p_{load-x,t}$, in bus x at time t and, f and w the number of buses and lines, respectively. In this way, the resilience index is much more precise in providing information about the amount of power or energy at risk. Including additional elements on the system, i.e., more buses and power lines, increases the denominator in the previous equation. The new elements would increase resilience if they were reducing the average energy or power at risk per element. At the same time, they would decrease resilience in case of an increase in the average energy or power at risk.

Second, the resilience index equation was not clear in the management of the number of hazards included in the hazard database. As mentioned, the element's energy/power at risk might exceed each element's impact, making this situation undesirable. Thus, the number of hazards, M , should be incorporated into the resilience index as follows:

$$\mathcal{R} = 1 - \frac{R_T}{I_T \cdot M} \quad (20)$$

As a result, including new hazards in the database should result in a more precise resilience index, but huge variations are avoided. Including a hazard with a lower hazard index than the average would slightly increase the resilience while including a hazard with a higher hazard index would decrease it. Otherwise, the inclusion of new hazards in the database would always result in a resilience decrease and, consequently, discourage its incorporation. Proceeding in this way, system stakeholders are encouraged to keep the database updated.

As a result, the current case study presents a resilience index of 98,89 % and 99,16 % for a winter and autumn average day, respectively.

At this point, the authors want to note that the power at risk and the global resilience index are highly dependent on various qualitative analyses. First, the hazard index is based on a qualitative investigation that evaluates the hazard intensity and probability. Second, the vulnerability likelihood is established on a 10-level scale based on the vulnerabilities determined from the currently available information. As a result, the same qualitative scales should be used to evaluate the impact of some mitigation action on the resilience index. Additionally, only systems that have been analyzed considering the same qualitative scales should be compared. Finally, high values in the resilience index, close to 100 %, are desirable. A resilience index lower than 50 % would mean that each element will produce a whole system's failure and, at least, 50 % of the hazards included in the database present a hazard index of 1. Values above 87,50 % should be common in developed networks. An 87,50 % value would mean that the average element's impact is half of the total demand, i.e., few elements supply the whole system's demand, each element presents a 50 % global vulnerability likelihood and the average hazard index is 0.5 for all hazards included in the database.

4.3 Resilience improvement through the MPC

The rural area analyzed in this work, with a single point connected to the main grid, showed some weaknesses that might affect the continuous power supply. The area presents a low but distributed population with various supply points. The population in the area is highly dependent on cars for essential needs, as big cities are some kilometers away. In that context, the electrical vehicle would increase the reliance on electrical supply. Although rural electrical networks do not supply many customers and the impact of an outage from an economic perspective is usually irrelevant, those networks are essential to keep the population in those territories. Traditional perspective would contemplate the introduction of diesel generators as backup systems. However, the new available technologies are opening a space to debate on new solutions.

MPCs might integrate three or more energy devices into a single according to [41]. In a context where the energy transition requires the introduction of converters in power systems, MPCs emerge as a promising technology to facilitate its integration while keeping projects economically feasible. IPlug's Deliverable 1.1. explored the main applications these converters might have on distribution networks from a technical perspective. Thanks to the GIS-base resilience approach, this work explores the MPCs potential in increasing the network's resilience while building the energy transition.

In iPlug's Deliverable 1.1. we reported the main case studies to explore MPCs. The network presented in this resilience-driven use case was pointed out as an interesting case study to evaluate the MPC potential on interconnecting two different voltage networks while accommodating better power management, as the 5 kV is interconnected to a 20 kV one. Although this case study is interesting from a technical point of view, the resilience evaluation addressed in the network concluded that this system might be an interesting case study to explore the coupling of MV lines that present the same voltage level. In this case, a third MPC port, which could be used to introduce renewables to the system, would be used to interconnect a Battery Energy Storage System (BESS). The BESS is introduced as a backup system. The BESS energy could keep the grid operating during power outages due to the MPC grid-forming mode.

The MPC location is determined considering the following three points. First, the MPC should allow the power flow from one feeder to the other when the main supply fails. Second, the two points connected should be relatively close. Third, the existing power stations should be used to minimize costs and to facilitate MPC inclusion in the system. From a resilience perspective, connecting the two feeders by their endpoints, i.e., Bus 32847 and Bus 34044, would reduce each element's impact to 0, increasing the resilience to 100 %. However, these points are more than 2 km one from the other. Consequently, the interconnection is not feasible from a technical and economical point of view.

Considering all this, the MPC would interconnect Bus 29265 with Bus 29490, which are the second most critical and the most technically feasible. Physically, those buses are MV cabins located in two power stations. Thus, although the MPC would be hosted in a separate building, new cabins would be included in those power stations. Each new cabin would be interconnected with one of the AC ports of

the MPC, Figure 77 shows the MPC electrical integration.

Figure 77: MPC integration in network

The MPC inclusion requires the following improvements in the system:

1. Two new MV cabins in existing Power Stations
2. One power station including 4 MV AC cabins, 1 LV DC protection box and the MPC
3. Two new power lines

Regarding the new power lines, considering the vulnerabilities investigation carried out in Section 4.1.4, underground power lines are much less vulnerable due to their lower exposure to the hazards included in the database. Consequently, new power lines would be installed underground.

The topology Figures 52 and 54 is modified according to Figure 78. The MPC is represented as two unconnected AC buses, interconnected to the existing infrastructure through the new power lines. The DC bus is not defined in the topology, as it is considered an internal MPC bus without impact on the system's dynamics. The power flow between the MPC terminals is assumed ideal, i.e., no losses considered between the terminals.

Figure 78: Network topology after MPC inclusion **Map scale:** 1 : 75 000, **Detail A:** 1 : 1 750.

Vulnerabilities

The new elements introduced, i.e., the MPC and the new power lines, aim to increase resilience. The resilience improvement would be a consequence of the element’s impact reduction, as they do not modify other element’s vulnerabilities and the hazards that might affect the region.

Although the new elements introduced, i.e., the MPC and the new power lines, aim to increase resilience, it cannot be omitted that they also present their vulnerabilities. This section develops two main investigations. First, we investigate the new element’s vulnerabilities. Second, each element’s impact is evaluated.

Likelihood

The vulnerabilities identified in this work have been considered in the MPC solution. Thus, technical solutions that present low vulnerability likelihood are preferred. As mentioned, this resulted in underground power lines, instead of overhead ones. Similarly, the new power station building includes LPS on both AC sides. Consequently, the MPC is protected in both AC sides.

Tables 57 and 58 present the global vulnerability likelihood established for the MPC nodes and the new power lines. The vulnerability likelihood is low for all hazards included in the database except for the subsurface machinery. As mentioned, underground power is the system’s weakest when this machinery is

operating in the area. Similarly, buses might be considered a weak point too. Although the MV cabins, installed in the new building, cannot be affected by the machinery operating, the building’s surrounding area, which can be included as part of the nodes, could be considered significantly vulnerable, as clearing work will be periodically performed.

	High-Access Machinery	Subsurface Machinery	Lightning	Wind	Wildfire
Buses	10%	90%	10%	10%	10%
Power Lines	10%	90%	10%	10%	10%

Table 57: Vulnerability likelihood of MPC Buses and new power lines once simple hazards are given.

	Vegetation + Wind	Lightning + Wind	Wildfire + Wind	Wildfire + Heatwave	Vegetation + Wind + Lighting	Vegetation + Wind + Wildfire
Buses	10%	10%	10%	10%	10%	10%
Power Lines	10%	10%	10%	10%	10%	10%

Table 58: Vulnerability likelihood of MPC Buses and new power lines once composed hazards are given.

The vulnerabilities described in Tables 57 and 58 will be included in the reported in Figures 71 and 72

Impact

As for the impact, the instantaneous AC OPF is used to determine how the MPC inclusion modifies the system’s dynamics in case of failure. The MPC can be taken as slack bus in each of its AC sites and even in both if necessary. Besides, the MPC can operate in a power factor close to 0 injecting only reactive power in some or both feeders. However, in this case, the MPC power factor is limited to 0.9 of its active power supplied. Figures 79 and 80 show the new element’s impact in winter and autumn, respectively.

Figure 79: Network’s impact evaluation after MPC introduction determined through an Hourly AC OPF considering winter power demand. **Map scale:** 1 : 100 000, **Detail A:** 1 : 150

Figure 80: Network’s impact evaluation after MPC introduction determined through an Hourly AC OPF considering autumn average power demand. **Map scale:** 1 : 100 000, **Detail A:** 1 : 150

Compared to Figures 73 and 74 the impact has been reduced in those elements close to the MPC. When the MPC is introduced, Bus 29278 turns into the most critical one, as it supplies the highest demand. As mentioned, the MPC can interconnect the two feeders and allow the power to flow through it. Besides, the MPC can actuate as a generator providing power from a BESS system installed on the MPC DC site. For a better understanding, the following lines include a discussion about the MPC operation in the system.

Figure 81 a) shows that when all elements are connected, the MPC is not operating. The new power lines do not carry any current.

The MPC cannot contribute to all failures. The impact of failures that occurred downstream of the MPC location cannot be minimized. Notwithstanding, the MPC introduces redundancy in the system and allows its operation when the most critical elements fail. We understand the most critical elements as the ones that carry the whole system’s demand or, at least, the whole feeders’ demand.

Figure 81 b) shows that the system remains in operation when the node connected to the main grid fails. The MPC provides power from the BESS installed in its DC port. Under this scenario, the power supplied by each AC port is adjusted to minimize the system’s losses and, consequently, minimize the

power supply by the BESS. The MPC takes advantage of the redundant power lines infrastructure to minimize losses. As a result, the current carried by each line is optimized. Figure 81 c) shows a similar operation. In this case, one node remains connected to the main grid. The node connected is the one that holds the PV system. As a result, from this node, energy is exported to the main grid.

The redundant infrastructure cannot be used when the node that joins the three overhead power lines fails, Figure 81 d). Under this scenario, the MPC should supply two isolated grids. As a result, each AC port provides the power demanded by the accessible feeder. In this operation mode, we can identify that the AC port connected to the northwestern feeder supplies a higher power due to the higher demand connected to the feeder.

As mentioned, the operation of the MPC is not limited to the BESS power supply, the MPC can facilitate the power flow between the southeastern and northwestern feeders. Figure 81 e) and f) show that, when the main line supplying the feeder fails, the MPC keeps the isolated feeder supplied. Under this scenario, the power line not affected by the failure should carry the whole system's demand. This situation is not critical in the current network due to the low demand. However, this situation should be carefully managed in systems where congestion problems might arise.

Figure 81: System’s operation during an element failure (in red) **Map scale:** 1 : 150 000, Detail A: 1 : 1 000, Detail B: 1 : 2 500

Resilience

The hazard database and the vulnerability likelihood of already existing elements have not been modified. The previous section investigated the likelihood of vulnerability of the four new elements introduced in the system, i.e., two buses and two power lines. Besides each element’s impact has been recalculated considering the MPC inclusion.

Considering all, this section examines the new system’s resilience. Figures 82 and 83 shows the

amount of power at risk in each system’s elements considering winter’s and autumn’s average power, respectively. These figures keep the same color scale as the one depicted in Figures 75 and 76 to facilitate the comparison between the two scenarios investigated, i.e., current system and MPC inclusion.

The MPC inclusion reduced the power at risk in elements close to the main grid’s connection point. Thanks to MPC, the total power at risk never exceeds the total demand. Thus, the criticalities observed in some elements of base resilience investigation are now non-critical.

Figure 82: Network’s risk assessment for an average winter hour after including the MPC. **Map scale:** 1 : 100 000, Detail A: 1 : 75.

Figure 83: Network’s risk assessment for an average autumn hour after including the MPC. **Map scale:** 1 : 100 000, Detail A: 1 : 75.

Regarding the resilience index, the introduction of the MPC increases the resilience index from 98,89 % to 99,40 % in winter and from 99,16 % to 99,54 % in autumn, as summarized in Table 59. Thus, the resilience increases by 0,51 % and 0,38 % in winter and autumn, respectively.

RESILIENCE INDEX COMPARISON		
Season	WITHOUT MPC	WITH MPC
winter	98,89%	99,40%
autumn	99,16%	99,54%

Table 59: Resilience index comparison without and with MPC included in the system.

Although the resilience index increase is limited, it is important to note the risk reduction shown in Figures 82 and 83. As mentioned, the resilience index should be close to 100 % in developed countries, especially when the hazards included are environmental and can be well modeled. The network’s evolution has intrinsically considered these hazards from the beginning, not because of resilience but to save costs and boost dependability.

MPC sizing

This section investigates the MPC and BESS size that would allow the resilience increase and the risk minimization.

Although in autumn the total demand is relatively lower than in winter, the average PV generation injected at Bus 27200 is higher in winter than in autumn. However, the overall demand is comparatively lower in the former. Thus, the MPC operation should be carefully evaluated in both seasons.

As described in Section 4.3, Bus 27200 remains connected to the main grid in some cases that the MPC operates due to the failure's location. The average active power demanded in Bus 27200 is 7,511 kW and 9,354 kW in autumn and winter, respectively. Regarding the average PV generation, it is 12,801 kW and 15,353 kW in autumn and winter, respectively.

Considering this, we can identify four cases in which the system is operating.

First, Bus 27200 is directly connected to the main grid and isolated from the system. In this case, the MPC injects 40,462 kW to the northwestern feeder and 8,870 kW to the southeastern one in autumn, and 40,767 kW and 8,821 kW in winter to each feeder respectively.

Second, Bus 27200 is connected to the system but the system is isolated from the main grid. Under this scenario, the MPC provides 36,370 kW and 34,342 kW to the northeastern feeder in autumn and winter, respectively, and 7,673 kW and 9,251 kW to the southwestern feeder in autumn and winter.

Third, the system is connected to the grid but the northeastern feeder cannot be supplied directly. In this case, the MPC transfers the power from the southwestern one. The average power transferred is 40,473 kW and 40,779 kW in autumn and winter, respectively.

Finally, the system is connected to the grid but the southwestern feeder cannot be supplied directly. In this case, the MPC transfers the power from the northeastern one. The average power transferred is 8,871 kW and 8,821 kW in autumn and winter, respectively.

To maximize the resilience increase, the MPC is sized considering the most critical results obtained. Thus, the MPC should be capable of managing 41 kW in each AC port to ensure the proper system's operation in all cases.

Regarding the BESS size, as this work does not explore the recovery time after being affected by each hazard, its capacity cannot be determined. The BESS power should be around 50 kW because, when the system is isolated from the grid, the MPC supplies power in the range of 41 kW and 9 kW to each AC port. When the system is connected to the grid, 37 kW are transferred from the MPC's AC ports in the most critical case. Consequently, the full utilization of BESS power would occur only in the event of a grid connection failure.

4.4 Final discussion

As mentioned, the resilience index in developed countries should be close to 100 % even in what we identify as weak networks. This is observed in the base case resilience. Thus, including certain technologies has a limited impact on resilience improvement. However, we consider that risk reduction should be considered

along with the resilience index. The power or energy at risk could provide information about the number of customers not supplied, the customers' type, or the risks' costs. Additionally, two different systems could have the same resilience index while the amount of power or energy at risk notably diverges.

The resilience analysis is based on qualitative analyses of hazards and the system's vulnerabilities. Thus, only the results obtained from analysis that consider the same qualitative scale should be compared. Otherwise, the conclusions drawn from the comparison might be inaccurate.

The main system's vulnerability is its dependency on the point connected to the main grid. Nonetheless, power lines and power stations are considered non-critical. Considering the system's demand, the network could be implemented in LV. However, as demand is dispersed over a wide territory, MV becomes a more convenient solution. Consequently, power lines and power stations have sufficient capacity to manage the system's demand being far from congestion situations.

The MPC allowed the interconnection of the two main feeders. As a result, the system is capable of supplying one feeder from the other. Additionally, a DC port is used to install a BESS system that provides energy in case of grid failure. Consequently, the system can operate in islanded mode. As a result, the MPC incorporation increased the resilience by 1 %. However, it is important to value the risk reduction. Without the MPC some elements risked more than the total demand. The MPC does not modify the hazards to which the system is exposed either the vulnerabilities of preexisting buses and power lines. However, its inclusion notably reduced the impact of some critical elements, as it provides redundancy in the system.

Although this work focused on MPC to increase resilience, a wide range of technologies might be tested through the proposed approach.

4.5 Future work

In the context of the iPlug project, we have developed a GIS-based resilience approach. This development resulted in three Python-based QGIS plug-ins, which can be downloaded and installed following the User Guide v2 included in Appendix B.4.

The methodology and the developed tools have been used to analyze a specific network provided by Anell, the regional DSO. In this document, we have evaluated the main hazards to which the system is exposed and its most relevant vulnerabilities, in terms of likelihood and impact. Afterward, we were able to characterize the base resilience and evaluate how the MPC could contribute to its improvement.

Resilience is a new wide concept, and there is still an open discussion in literature about the methodologies used. This work is a starting point, but resilience studies should always go deeper to provide the most accurate system picture. In that context, we identify four main lines to continue the current work.

First, cascade events modelization. In the current approach, we consider the probability of combined hazards. However, how the occurrence of a hazard might produce a second one a certain time later has not been evaluated. Similarly, the current approach determines each element's impact comparing the amount of power or energy supplied when all elements are in operation with the amount of power

or energy supplied when the analyzed element fails. Consequently, cascade failures are not currently modeled.

Second, the recovery time after being affected by each kind of hazard has not been evaluated. This work considers, through the hazard index, the probability of being affected by a certain hazard of a specific intensity. However, this does not provide information about the recovery time. Some hazards might affect the system during seconds, others during minutes and the most critical ones during hours or even days. The recovery time would be essential information to accurately size various mitigating procedures, such the BESS capacity.

Third, in critical systems, where congestion problems might be erased, an Energy Management System (EMS) would be essential to maximize the energy supplied to the loads. Therefore, while evaluating the element's influence, the EMS operation should be taken into account.

Fourth, in this work, we have characterized the resilience considering the amount of power or energy supplied. However, other variables such as the cost or the number of vulnerable customers not supplied could provide complementary information. In the following stages, we will investigate how those metrics could be included in the resilience perspective.

In parallel, the resilience approach, and its improved versions, will be used to analyze other new technologies that will or might play a relevant role in the future power systems from a resilience perspective.

5 Conclusions

In this work, we have applied the developed methodologies to optimally size and locate the MPC. In each use case, we have evaluated various MPC functionalities. As a result, this document provides a wide range of MPC applications in actual networks.

An optimization-based methodology is applied to five use cases to analyse the system operation and obtain the nominal power of the MPC terminals. Among the different use cases, we concluded that the MPC terminal connected to the EV is determined by the load peak and that the amount of PV connected to the MPC highly affects the nominal power of the other MPC terminals.

First, three building applications are analyzed where the MPC can integrate PV, EV and BESS. In general, we concluded that the main load and the grid should be connected to the same MPC terminal, so if power goes from the grid to the load it doesn't have to go through the MPC. These cases have low PV penetration, as the available PV generation represents less than 16 % the annual load. Therefore the BESS is used to reduce operational costs, which are considered the cost of buying energy to the grid. For this application, we can conclude that the BESS is not cost-effective unless its cost is very low and the price of energy from the grid is high. A comparison was also performed between the MPC and connecting each appliance through back-to-back converters together with a sensitivity analysis on the costs considered for these power electronics. In that sense, we concluded that the MPC cost of each terminal, supposing all terminals have the same, should be between 43 and 55 % less than the converter cost to be economically feasible, depending on the use case and for a range between 50 and 250 €/kW.

Then, a LV use case was analyzed, where the MPC is used to interconnect two lines at different voltage levels and integrate PV and EV into the network. A two-terminal MPC use only for interconnection enables active power exchange between the networks and provides reactive power support. Although in this case, the MPC nominal power obtained is very small compared to the network loads. The PV integration through the MPC is the main factor that affects the system operation and MPC nominal powers. Renewable generation is prioritized, although some curtailment can appear, and power losses on the lines are also considered. This results in having a MPC terminal connected to the 400 V network with twice as much nominal power than the terminal connected to the 230 V network to evacuate the PV generation.

Next, a MV use case was analyzed, where the MPC is used to interconnect two lines. First, an analysis was performed on the factors that can influence the MPC sizing. We concluded that the MPC nominal power of the terminals tends to increase linearly with higher voltage differences between the buses before their interconnection when losses or the voltage difference is minimized. Later, a MV use case provided by Anell was analyzed, where the MPC aims to reduce the voltage difference between the buses to which it is connected. According to the importance of this objective in the optimization, the resulting nominal power of the MPC terminals can increase significantly. Also, the MPC can provide better improvements in the system operation when the load of the lines is very different and the voltage differences between the buses before their interconnection is higher.

Through the GIS-based resilience approach, we have explored how the MPC might contribute to the network's resilience increase. Among the various MPC applications, we concluded that its capacity to interconnect various power lines while introducing backup elements is the most convenient. Thus, we proposed a 3-port MPC: two AC and one DC. The AC ports are used to interconnect two MV power lines while the DC port facilitates the introduction of a BESS.

From the resilience analysis, four main conclusions are drawn.

First, the resilience is highly dependent on the hazard database. To have an accurate database, data from many institutions must be included. One of the main challenges is making the various types of data and language comparable. In this work, we have established a qualitative scale to compare all hazards included. Nonetheless, only systems that consider the same qualitative scale in the hazards database would be comparable.

Second, vulnerabilities are not objective. The system's technical characteristics are neither strong nor weak, its evaluation depends on the context. Thus, the same solution might be extremely weak when a certain hazard occurs and strong when another happens. An accurate vulnerability evaluation requires detailed network information. This is concluded as one of the main challenges for the DSOs and TSOs.

Third, resilience is not an absolute measure. Resilience is based on qualitative and subjective analysis. Thus, if resilience wanted to become an absolute and comparable measure worldwide, standardization would be essential. The resilience standardization would, in turn, require the standardization of the database provided by many local, regional, and global institutions. As this seems not feasible shortly, resilience studies must include information about the qualitative scales used.

Fourth, for the actual use case considered and with the context presented in the document, overhead power lines were concluded as the most vulnerable system elements. As for the system's resilience, a lower resilience index is obtained in winter, compared to autumn due to the higher wind hazards. Finally, the MPC contributed to risk mitigation and resilience increase. The resilience index increased by 1 % in winter when the MPC was included. Additionally, the amount of power at risk in each element has been notably reduced.

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Annex

B.1 Resilience methodology

Resilience has become a fundamental concept in power systems. In 2012, the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) published a Special Report to manage the risks that might arise due to extreme weather conditions [42]. Resilience is defined as "the ability of a system and its component parts to anticipate, absorb, accommodate, or recover from the effects of a hazardous event in a timely and efficient manner, including through the preservation, restoration, or improvement of its essential basic structures and functions". The report also recognizes the vulnerabilities of the power systems and how this might impact keeping the supply to all consumers.

In that context, in 2015, the European Joint Research Center (JRC) published the report *Building a Resilient Europe in a Globalised World* [43]. The report addresses the necessity of an interdisciplinary approach to building a resilient European Union (EU). In 2020, the "2020 Strategic Foresight Report" was published [44] introducing resilience as a new concept for EU policies. Later, Regulation (EU) 2021/241 [45] and Regulation (EU) 2023/43 [46] introduced some measures to address the European recovery after COVID-19 and the Ukraine's war crisis. In these regulations, the resilience of the transmission and distribution networks is identified as a crucial element to guarantee system flexibility, minimize congestion, and ensure supply chains, among others.

In the US, the Department of Energy is focused on the modernization and expansion of the electricity grid to integrate renewable energies while increasing resilience [47]. In this line, the US Department of Energy's National Renewable Energy Laboratory (NREL) defines resilience as "The ability to anticipate, prepare for, and adapt to changing conditions and withstand, respond to, and recover rapidly from disruptions through adaptable and holistic planning and technical solutions" [48].

Considering the importance of resilience in power systems [49] proposes a specific definition and quantification methods of resilience in power systems. The authors distinguish between two-time horizons: operational or short-term and infrastructural or long-term. In both horizons, resilience is linked to risk-based approaches to evaluate both the potential disruptive events and the weaknesses of the infrastructure.

In that context, this project developed a GIS-based approach to assess the resilience of planning power systems. Thus, the authors identified GIS as a promising system for managing the information related to networks. The proposed methodology relies on the framework developed by NREL [50], which stems from a comprehensive risk assessment. Thus, this methodology discerns between hazards and vulnerabilities. Disruptive events that may impact the infrastructure without being controllable define hazards. In turn, weaknesses relate to vulnerabilities and are determined by their likelihood of occurrence when a hazard is present and the potential impact they may cause. A GIS system effectively manages multiple layers of information, providing a realistic representation of the system's characteristics and potential hazards.

This annex describes the GIS-based methodology proposed to evaluate the network's resilience, summarized in Figure 85 and described along the following subsections.

The following terms are used to describe the methodology:

- **LAYER:** Visual geospatial data representation within a digital mapping environment. Each layer is a vector of features.
- **FEATURE:** Any area or element of the Earth's surface that can be represented on a map. Features are, mainly, points, lines and polygons. Apart from its geographic representation, features can include additional information about the elements. The additional information is defined through attributes.
- **ATTRIBUTES:** Nonspatial properties of a feature. Attributes are characterized by **FIELD** and **VALUE**. The **FIELD** is the name of the property and the **VALUE** the property itself. **VALUE** can include numerical, alphanumeric, or descriptive information.
- **TABULAR DATA:** Nonspatial descriptive information stored in rows and columns. Tabular data can be joined to spatial data. Each row would be linked to a feature and each column would be an attribute. The column name would correspond to the attribute's field and each row value's to each attribute's value.

Hazards

This section describes the procedure for building the hazard database, symbolized by **H**. The hazard database **H** is a set of layers defined as $\mathbf{H} = [\mathbf{h}_1, \mathbf{h}_2, \dots, \mathbf{h}_m, \dots, \mathbf{h}_M]$ where \mathbf{h}_m represents a layer that defines a hazard included in the database and M the total number of layers of the set. Each layer includes the necessary features to characterize the hazard in a certain region. Four attributes are expected in each layer that would define the probability of occurrence in each year's season.

Figure 84 describes the database development process. First, hazards that might affect an electrical system should be compiled and included in **H**. Second, an iterative process is required to identify all hazards that might occur simultaneously. Once two potential simultaneous hazards are identified the combined probability should be determined based on the relation between the hazards:

- $P(A \cap A') = P(A'|A) \cdot P(A) \rightarrow$ Dependent Events
- $P(A \cap A') = P(A) \cdot P(A') \rightarrow$ Independents Events

where A and A' are two layers, \mathbf{h}_m , of **H**. The hazard database **H** is completed when all potentially simultaneous events are identified or the combined probability can be considered negligible.

Figure 84: Hazards Database

Vulnerabilities Analysis

The vulnerability analysis focuses on a specific electrical network, \mathbf{N} .

The network \mathbf{N} is a set of two layers, $\mathbf{N} = [\mathbf{f}, \mathbf{w}]$, where \mathbf{f} and \mathbf{w} are layers that provide information

related to buses and power lines, respectively. Regarding the type of features, \mathbf{f} includes points (one per bus) and \mathbf{w} lines (one per power line). Layers \mathbf{f} and \mathbf{w} include as attributes the technical characteristics of each system's element, represented by a feature in the layer.

The vulnerabilities can be characterized once the system, \mathbf{N} , is defined. The vulnerability analysis involves three main steps: vulnerability identification, likelihood characterization, and impact calculations.

As for vulnerability identification, the process might involve the different system's stakeholders. This process results in a list of vulnerabilities v for each system's element.

The presence of a vulnerability does not necessarily mean that the system will be compromised. Thus, the likelihood of being affected by a vulnerability varies depending on the hazard. Consequently, a specific vulnerability likelihood should be determined for each event included in the hazard database and for each vulnerability identified, h , $\mathbf{L}_{\mathbf{v},\mathbf{h}}$. The vector $\mathbf{L}_{\mathbf{v},\mathbf{h}}$ is a set of two tabular data, $\mathbf{L}_{\mathbf{v},\mathbf{h}} = [\mathbf{l}\text{-}\mathbf{f}_{\mathbf{v},\mathbf{h}}, \mathbf{l}\text{-}\mathbf{w}_{\mathbf{v},\mathbf{h}}]$, for buses and power lines, respectively. $\mathbf{l}\text{-}\mathbf{f}_{\mathbf{v},\mathbf{h}}$ and $\mathbf{l}\text{-}\mathbf{w}_{\mathbf{v},\mathbf{h}}$ have as many columns as hazards included in \mathbf{H} and as many rows as vulnerabilities per element.

The impact, \mathbf{I} , is set of two tabular data, $\mathbf{I} = [\iota\text{-}\mathbf{f}, \iota\text{-}\mathbf{w}]$, for buses and power lines, respectively. The layers $\iota\text{-}\mathbf{f}$ and $\iota\text{-}\mathbf{w}$ have as many rows as features included in \mathbf{f} and \mathbf{w} , respectively, a single column that provides the impact of each element is included. The impact that each element might have on the system can be quantified from technological, economic or social perspectives. This work defines the impact, \mathbf{I} , of an element through the amount of energy not supplied when the element is not in service. Thus, an Optimal Power Flow (OPF) approach is proposed to quantify the impact. The technical parameters required to perform the OPF are obtained from the attributes of \mathbf{f} and \mathbf{w} . The OPF objective function maximizes the energy supplied by the system, that is:

$$[\max] \sum_x \sum_t p_{load-x,t} \quad (21)$$

where $p_{load-x,t}$ is the power supplied from bus x at time t . Loads are assumed to be connected in a specific bus x . A bus x can be lost because of a specific issue in the bus itself or due to the loss of a power line that feeds it. Thus, the impact of each element, bus or power line, is determined by the difference between the total energy supplied when all elements are in service and the total energy supplied when the element is not in service.

Risk Assessment and Resilience analysis

After developing the hazard database, \mathbf{H} , for a specific region and evaluating the vulnerabilities, $\mathbf{L}_{\mathbf{v},\mathbf{h}}$, and impact, \mathbf{I} , of a system, \mathbf{N} , the risk assessment methodology provides information about the criticality of each element and the global system resilience, as shown in Figure 85.

First, the power lines included in layer w of the network \mathbf{N} , are segmented, if required, to provide more detailed information. In this way, the network defined as $\mathbf{N} = [\mathbf{f}, \mathbf{w}]$ turns into $\mathbf{N} = [\mathbf{f}, \mathbf{w}\text{-}\mathbf{q}]$ where

q expresses the number of segments of each power line. The topology of $\mathbf{w-q}$ is the same as \mathbf{w} . However, more features are included to define the same system. Besides, the segment's length is included in the attributes of the layer.

Second, the extension of the hazard database is adjusted to the system's regions. As a result, the number of features included in each $\mathbf{h_m}$ could be reduced and the computational time required is optimized.

Third, the intersections between the geospatial data of the system, \mathbf{N} , and the hazard database, \mathbf{H} , are evaluated for a certain season of the year. As a result, a new set of layers is created, $\mathbf{P_h} = [\rho\text{-}\mathbf{f_h}, \rho\text{-}\mathbf{w-q_h}]$. $\rho\text{-}\mathbf{f_h}$ and $\rho\text{-}\mathbf{w-q_h}$ include the same geospatial data and attributes as \mathbf{f} and $\mathbf{w-q}$, respectively, and add one attribute per hazard $\mathbf{h_m}$. The field of each new attribute is the hazard's name and the value is the element's probability of being affected by hazard, $\mathbf{h_m}$. The probability is taken from hazard's attributes.

Fourth, the tabular data obtained from the vulnerability analysis, $\mathbf{L_{v,h}}$ and \mathbf{I} , are combined to the geospatial data of $\mathbf{P_h}$ through each element's name. The energy at risk in each bus and power line is determined as follows:

$$\mathbf{r-f} = \sum_h \sum_v \rho\text{-}\mathbf{f_h} \cdot \mathbf{l-f_{v,h}} \cdot \iota\text{-}\mathbf{f} \quad (22)$$

$$\mathbf{r-w-q} = \sum_h \sum_v \rho\text{-}\mathbf{w-q_h} \cdot \mathbf{l-w_{v,h}} \cdot \iota\text{-}\mathbf{w} \cdot \frac{\mathbf{s_l}}{\mathbf{l}} \quad (23)$$

where $\mathbf{s_l}$ is a vector of the segment's length and \mathbf{l} the power line's total length. This factor is considered because of the power lines segmentation performed in the first stage. $\mathbf{r-f}$ and $\mathbf{r-w-q}$ are two layers included in the set of layers \mathbf{R} . Their topology is the same as \mathbf{N} . However, as attributes, the layers provide the amount of energy at risk.

Finally, a resilience index, \mathcal{R} , for the whole system is determined based on the total energy risked and the aggregated impact as follows:

$$R_T = 1 - \sum \mathbf{r-f} + \sum \mathbf{r-w-q} \quad (24)$$

$$I_T = \sum \iota\text{-}\mathbf{f} + \sum \iota\text{-}\mathbf{w} \quad (25)$$

$$\mathcal{R} = 1 - \frac{R_T}{I_T} \quad (26)$$

where R_T is the total energy at risk in the system. R_T is obtained by summing the amount of energy at risk in each element provided from the attributes of \mathbf{R} . In turn, I_T is the sum of the partial impacts identified in the system. I_T is obtained by summing the partial impacts provided from the attributes of \mathbf{I} . As a result, \mathcal{R} is a numerical index that determines the global system’s resilience. This variable enables the comparison of different systems.

Figure 85: Risk Assessment and Resilience Analysis

B.2 GEOVEG categories

No.	GEOVEG classification	Type	Area (ha)
1	Mountain oaks in silicic terrain, Catalan and Occitan	evergreen oak	1426,664
2	Lowland oak groves with pines (<i>Pinus</i> spp.)	evergreen oak	185,514
3	Mountain oak groves in calcareous terrain, from the Eastern Pyrenees and from the Ruscinic, Holositanic and Catalan territories	evergreen oak	139,463
4	Lowland oak trees, Catalan and Occitan	evergreen oak	119,988
5	Oak groves with oaks (<i>Quercus faginea</i> , <i>Q. pubescens</i> ...), lowland and submontane	evergreen oak	92,393
6	Fields conditioned as intensive pasture, dry or slightly moist	meadows	91,383
7	Mountain oak groves with pines (<i>Pinus</i> spp.)	evergreen oak	72,747
8	Heaths dominated by boal heather (<i>Erica arborea</i>), silicicolous, of the coasts and dry soils of the maritime Mediterranean regions	scrub	70,001
9	Oak maquis (<i>Quercus ilex</i>), acidophilic, lowland and Mediterranean mountain	scrub	54,874
10	Calcareous beeches, xeromesophilic, of the low-rainy middle mountains	common beech	53,161
11	Extensive dryland, mountain herbaceous crops	herbaceous crops	38,361
12	Martin oak (<i>Quercus pubescens</i>), calcareous, middle mountain forests and equivalent communities	sessile oak	34,391
13	Oak forests (<i>Quercus pubescens</i> , <i>Q. × cerrioides</i>), often with oaks (<i>Q. ilex</i>), lowland	sessile oak	33,917
14	Extensive herbaceous crops of wet soils (often irrigated or very rainy regions)	herbaceous crops	33,590
15	Landes de godua (<i>Sarothamnus scoparius</i>), acidophilic and mesophilic, of the rainy middle mountains (and lowlands)	meadows	28,279
16	Vernedes (sometimes pollancreds) with dead nettle (<i>Lamium flexuosum</i>), from the rainy lowland and the submontane stage	Populus or similar	27,194

No.	GEOVEG classification	Type	Area (ha)
17	Silicic and xerophilic meadows, with <i>Agrostis capillaris</i> , <i>Seseli montanum</i> , <i>Festuca ovina</i> , <i>Dichanthium ischaemum</i> ..., of the mid-Pyrenean mountains and Montseny	meadows	27,062
18	Balegars (thickets of <i>Genista balansae</i>), silicic, in dry, often sunny places, in the mountain stage	scrub	25,526
19	Ferns (populations of <i>Pteridium aquilinum</i>), mesohygrophilous and acidophilic, of the middle mountains (and of the subalpine stage)	scrub	23,043
20	Hedges with brambles (<i>Rubus ulmifolius</i>), dogwood (<i>Prunus spinosa</i>), dogwoods (<i>Rosa</i> spp.)..., mesoxerophilous, linked to rather dry forests, of the low-rainy middle mountains	thicket	20,846
21	Pyrenean Occitan acidophilic beech trees	common beech	20,149
22	Urbanizations and residential areas	others	16,719
23	Scots pine forests (<i>Pinus sylvestris</i>), neutrobasophiles and mesophiles, of the Pyrenees and the northern regions	pine	14,096
24	Timonedes (low bushes) dominated by thymus (<i>Thymus</i> spp.), sajolida (<i>Satureja montana</i>), sparbonella (<i>Sideritis scordioides</i>) or other labiades (lavender yeast), calcareous, low ground	scrub	13,820
25	Pine forests of Scots pine (<i>Pinus sylvestris</i>), with undergrowth of maquis or Mediterranean scrub	pine	11,424
26	Late Pirinen mesophilous beeches	common beech	11,180
27	Abandoned crops	herbaceous crops	9,958
28	Pinus pine (<i>Pinus pinea</i>) pine forests, often with an understory of scrub or acidophilic thickets, from the Catalan lowlands	pine	9,580
29	Hedges with brambles (<i>Rubus</i> spp.), gooseberries (<i>Prunus spinosa</i>)..., mesophilous, linked to beech and other mesohygrophilous forests, from the middle rainy mountains	thicket	8,901
30	<i>Juniperus communis</i> junipers, little or very dense, colonizing middle mountain pastures	scrub	8,088
31	Chestnuts, acidophilic, from the mid-mountain and lowlands	chestnut	6,861

No.	GEOVEG classification	Type	Area (ha)
32	Oak forests (<i>Quercus pubescens</i> or hybrids), silicic, from the middle mountains	sessile oak	6,296
33	Ruderal mountain communities	meadows	5,203
34	Aspen (<i>Populus tremula</i> woodlands), mesophyllous, often without forest understory, of the mid-mountain (and sclerophyll forest country)	aspen	4,697
35	Mixed forests of martin oak (<i>Quercus pubescens</i>) and Scots pine (<i>Pinus sylvestris</i>), calcareous, in the middle mountains	sessile oak	4,554
36	Fenassars (Meadows of <i>Brachypodium phoenicoides</i>), with <i>Euphorbia serrata</i> , <i>Galium lucidum</i> (white spurge)..., xeromesophiles, of deep lowland and low Mediterranean mountain soils	meadows	4,349
37	Oak (<i>Quercus ilex</i>), calcareous, lowland and Mediterranean mountain maquis	scrub	4,253
38	Ash trees of the Pyrenees and the northern Catalan mountains	ash	2,750
39	Forests of sessile oak (<i>Quercus petraea</i>), sometimes with other deciduous (<i>Betula pendula</i> ...), acidophilic and xeromesophilic, Pyrenees and northern Catalan territory	sessile oak	2,707
40	Extensive dryland, lowland herbaceous crops	herbaceous crops	2,649
41	Poplar plantations (<i>Populus</i> spp.)	<i>Populus</i> or similar	2,517
42	Boixedes (<i>Buxus sempervirens</i> thickets) of the middle mountains (and the Mediterranean regions)	scrub	2,261
43	Juniper thickets (<i>Juniperus nana</i>), on sunny slopes of the subalpine stage	scrub	2,186
44	Pedrusques from the lower Mediterranean mountains, Catalan-Occitan	rocky areas	2,101
45	Hazelnuts (<i>Corylus avellana</i> forests), with <i>Polystichum setiferum</i> ..., mesohygrophilous, from the ravines and very shady bottoms of the lowland (and the submontane stage)	common hazel	1,806
46	Heaps of rubble and slag	others	1,574
47	Meadows of therophytes (<i>Aira caryophyllea</i> , <i>Vulpia myuros</i> , <i>Filago minima</i> , <i>Trifolium arvense</i> ...), siliceous and often with sandy soils, in the middle mountains	meadows	1,496

No.	GEOVEG classification	Type	Area (ha)
48	Scots pine (<i>Pinus sylvestris</i>), acidophilic and xerophilic forests, in the montane and submontane regions	pine	1,315
49	Meadows with fromental (<i>Arrhenatherum elatius</i>), from the submontane and montane areas	meadows	1,173
50	Lawns within large parks or gardens	others	1,144
51	Fields of blackberry (<i>Calluna vulgaris</i>), often with <i>Genista pilosa</i> , <i>Genista anglica</i> ..., silicic soils, from the mountain and subalpine regions of the Pyrenees and the northern Catalan mountains	meadows	1,133
52	Joncedes (meadows, often covered, of <i>Aphyllanthes monspeliensis</i>), calcareous, of the Mediterranean regions and the low-rainy middle mountains	meadows	1,037
53	Scots pine forests (<i>Pinus sylvestris</i>), or regrowths, without forest undergrowth	pine	0,816
54	Gatelledes (forests, generally low, of <i>Salix atrocinerea</i>), with <i>Equisetum telmateia</i> , <i>Carex pendula</i> ..., at the bottom of ravines and depressions, with wet soil, in the Catalan territory	grey willow	0,805
55	Home gardens and orchards	others	0,675
56	Lowland ruderal communities	meadows	0,558
57	Pinassa pine groves (<i>Pinus nigra</i> subsp. <i>salzmannii</i>), or repopulations, without forest undergrowth	pine	0,550
58	Roads and communication hubs and other open spaces	others	0,446
59	Elderberry (<i>Sambucus nigra</i> thickets), with <i>vidalba</i> (<i>Clematis vitalba</i>), bramble (<i>Rubus ulmifolius</i>)..., hygrophilous and subnitrophilous, linked mainly to riparian forests	scrub	0,381
60	Pine groves of white pine (<i>Pinus halepensis</i>), with an undergrowth of maquis or oak or hornbeam scrub	pine	0,372
61	Siliceous rocks colonized by lichens, not littoral	rocky areas	0,316
62	Silicic and mesophilic meadows, with <i>Agrostis capillaris</i> , <i>Festuca nigrescens</i> , <i>Anthoxanthum odoratum</i> (scented gram), <i>Galium verum</i> (yellow gorse), <i>Genistella sagittalis</i> (peanut)..., from the mountain and subalpine areas of the Pyrenees	meadows	0,289
63	Reed beds always flooded	aquatic environment	0,284

No.	GEOVEG classification	Type	Area (ha)
64	Calcareous rocks with chasmophytic, thermophilic vegetation from the Mediterranean regions	rocky areas	0,266
65	High orchards, mainly irrigated, especially crops of apples (<i>Pyrus malus</i>), peaches (<i>Prunus persica</i>), pears (<i>Pyrus communis</i>) and other rosaceae	tall fruit crops	0,238
66	Archaeological sites	others	0,237
67	Siliceous rocks, with asarina (<i>Antirrhinum asarina</i>)..., from the rainy mountain stage (and from the cool low-land places)	rocky areas	0,190
68	Walnut fields (<i>Juglans regia</i>)	meadows	0,149
69	Plantations of cypress trees (<i>Cupressus sempervirens</i>) and other European cupressaceae	cypress	0,121
70	Industrial, agricultural freshwater ponds, large canals and ornamental ponds	aquatic environment	0,118
71	Trees and thickets of exotic species (<i>Ailanthus</i> , <i>Broussonetia</i> , <i>Celtis</i> , <i>Retama monosperma</i> ...)	scrub	0,063
72	Balengars (thickets of <i>Genista balansae</i>), siliceous, in dry, often sunny places, in the mountain stage	scrub	0,053
73	Low ground omissions	elms	0,048
74	Joncedes (meadows, often covered, of <i>Aphyllanthes monspeliensis</i>), calcareous, of the Mediterranean regions and the low-rainy middle mountains	meadows	0,033
75	Submerged populations of asprelles (<i>Chara</i> spp.), in ponds and ponds with carbonated water	aquatic environment	0,030
76	Pioneering vegetation, with sedges (<i>Sempervivum</i> spp.) and crespinnells (<i>Sedum</i> spp.), on siliceous terraprim, in the montane and subalpine areas	scrub	0,030
77	Mesotrophic stagnant fresh waters	aquatic environment	0,028
78	Forests of young deciduous trees, from regrowth or colonization, initial stages of the forest	deciduous trees	0,028
79	Pools and ponds in large parks or gardens	aquatic environment	0,022
80	Submerged communities of small or medium grasses (<i>Potamogeton densus</i> and other water spikes, <i>Elodea</i> , <i>Najas</i> , <i>Zannichellia</i> , <i>Ceratophyllum</i> ...), of stagnant freshwater	meadows	0,021

No.	GEOVEG classification	Type	Area (ha)
81	Plantations of cedars (<i>Cedrus</i> spp.) and other non-European pine trees (except pines)	cedar	0,018
82	Ash groves of <i>Fraxinus angustifolia</i> , low ground	ash	0,016
83	<i>Juniperus communis</i> junipers, little or very dense, colonizing heather or briar fields	meadows	0,014
84	Lowland silicic thickets (steppes and thickets)	scrub	0,013
85	Plantations of bananas (<i>Platanus orientalis</i> var. <i>acerifolia</i>) and other planifolia trees in moist soils	platanus	0,011
86	Reeds (of <i>Arundo donax</i>), on the water's edge	aquatic environment	0,008
87	Calcareous and mesophilic meadows, with <i>Festuca nigrescens</i> , <i>Plantago media</i> (plantation), <i>Galium verum</i> (yellow gorse), <i>Cirsium acaule</i> ..., from the mid-mountain and subalpine stage of the Pyrenees and nearby lands	meadows	0,008
88	Mountain steppe steppes (<i>Cistus laurifolius</i>), acidophilic, of the Pyrenees and the northern Catalan territory	scrub	0,006
89	Slats (dry meadows of <i>Brachypodium retusum</i>), with therophytes, silicicolous, low ground	meadows	0,006
90	Floating populations of <i>Lemna</i> spp. (water lentils), <i>Azolla caroliniana</i> or <i>Riccia</i> , from stagnant fresh waters, more or less eutrophic	aquatic environment	0,005
91	Brushes with an abundance of borrera steppe (<i>Cistus salviifolius</i>), calcareous, low-lying land	scrub	0,005
92	Oak thickets (<i>Quercus coccifera</i>), without or almost no thermophilic plants	scrub	0,005
93	Brushes dominated by black sedge (<i>Calicotome spinosa</i>), siliceous, from the maritime Mediterranean regions	scrub	0,005
94	Populations of barbs (<i>Typha</i> spp.)	aquatic environment	0,004
v 95	Hedges with gorse (<i>Coriaria myrtifolia</i>), bramble (<i>Rubus ulmifolius</i>)..., of lowland (and of the mountain stage)	thicket	0,004
96	Formations of elderberry (<i>Sambucus racemosa</i>), cattail (<i>Salix caprea</i>), raspberry (<i>Rubus idaeus</i>)..., in the forest clearings, in the subalpine (and mountain)	scrub	0,002
97	True broom brooms (<i>Spartium junceum</i>), from the Mediterranean regions (especially the maritime ones)	meadows	0,002

No.	GEOVEG classification	Type	Area (ha)
98	Shaded calcareous rocks, with comophytic vegetation of mosses and ferns, from the mountain stage and the Mediterranean mountains	rocky areas	0,002
99	Shaded siliceous rocks, with comophytic vegetation of mosses and ferns, from the Mediterranean regions	rocky areas	0,002
100	Meadows with <i>Cynosurus cristatus</i> , mesophiles, intensively grazed	meadows	0,001
101	Savanoid meadows of beehive (<i>Hyparrhenia hirta</i>), on sunny slopes of the maritime regions	meadows	0,001
102	Wet limestone rocks and drips, with falzia (<i>Adiantum capillus-veneris</i>), from the Mediterranean regions	rocky areas	0,001
103	Rocks and walls with subnitrophilic vegetation	rocky areas	0,001
104	Shaded siliceous rocks, with comophytic vegetation of mosses and ferns, of the mountain stage	rocky areas	0,001
105	Mines and underground tunnels	others	0,000
106	Junkeroles of <i>Juncus bufonius</i> , from temporarily flooded soils of the mountain stage	aquatic environment	0,000
107	Sedge sedges (<i>Scirpus holoschoenus</i>) and graminoid, hygrophilous, lowland (and mid-mountain) grasses	scrub	0,000
108	Fountain communities often dominated by cardamines (<i>Cardamine</i> spp.)..., of white water, often shaded, in mountain and subalpine areas	meadows	0,000
109	Meadows of <i>Sedum album</i> and other crespinnells, of terraprim and rocky ledges, calcareous, of the middle mountains	meadows	0,000

B.3 Combined hazards layers

Figure 86: Lightning & Wind combined hazard **a)** winter, **b)** spring, **c)** summer, **d)** autumn. **Area evaluated:** Case study region. **Map scale:** 1 : 200 000.

Figure 87: Wind & Wildfire combined hazard **a)** winter, **b)** spring, **c)** summer, **d)** autumn. **Area evaluated:** Case study region. **Map scale:** 1 : 200 000.

Figure 88: Wildfire & Heatwave combined hazard **a)** winter, **b)** spring, **c)** summer, **d)** autumn. **Area evaluated:** Case study region. **Map scale:** 1 : 200 000.

Figure 89: Vegetation & Wind & Lightning combined hazard **a)** winter, **b)** spring, **c)** summer, **d)** autumn. **Area evaluated:** Case study region. **Map scale:** 1 : 200 000.

Figure 90: Vegetation & Wind & Wildfire combined hazard **a)** winter, **b)** spring, **c)** summer, **d)** autumn. **Area evaluated:** Case study region. **Map scale:** 1 : 200 000.

B.4 Daily average consumption profiles per season

(a)

(b)

(c)

(d)

(e)

(f)

(g)

(h)

(i)

(j)

(k)

(l)

(m)

(n)

(o)

(p)

(q)

(r)

(s)

(t)

(u)

(v)

(w)

(x)

(y)

Figure 91: Daily average profiles per season in MV aggregated consumption buses

Annex: Python-based QGIS plug-ins USER GUIDE v2

Three Python-based QGIS plug-ins are developed in the context of the iPlug project to address the network's resilience.

1. **Hazard Combination** → This Plugin creates a new layer providing the probability of occurrence of a combined event from simple events. The user should indicate the type of relation between events: dependent or independent.
2. **Impact Evaluation** → This Plugin determines the impact of each element based on an OPF analysis. The user should introduce one layer for buses and one for power lines. The Attribute Table of each layer should include the required parameters to perform the OPF analysis. Besides, the user can select the type of OPF (AC or DC) and the simulation (24-hour profile or instantaneous). As a result, the Plugin created two new layers, one for buses and one for power lines. Each new layer includes, in the attribute table, the impact of each element in power or energy, depending on the simulation type selected. Finally, the Plugin provides a spreadsheet with the same information.
3. **Risk Assessment and Resilience Index** → This Plugin evaluates power/energy at risk in each element based on the hazards that might affect a system and its vulnerabilities. First, the user should indicate the year's season to perform the analysis. Then, the maximum power line's segment length. Finally, the user should upload a spreadsheet with the system's vulnerabilities.

Please, follow the stages described in this User Guide when using the Plugins, otherwise, the results may not be as expected.

C.1 Installation

C.1.1 Permission access

The Plugins are available in a GitHub private repository. We ask new users to request permission access from the iPlug administration to continue.

You can obtain permission by emailing montserrat.montala@upc.edu indicating an Affiliation Link and the purpose of the request.

C.1.2 General Requirements

- **QGIS \geq 3.0:** Download from [QGIS OfficialSite](#).

C.1.3 Recommended additional Plugins

- **Plugin Reloader:** Download from [Plugin Reloader OfficialSite](#).

C.1.4 Specific requirement for → Impact Evaluation

- **Pandapower \geq 6.4:**
 - Open OSGeo4W shell (packed with QGIS in the start menu)
 - Install the library using “pip”, following the instructions at the [Pandapower OfficialSite](#).

C.1.5 Plugin Installation steps

- Download from the repository the required Plugin.
- Unzip the folder.
- Save the folder in the QGIS’ Active User Profile.
 - Linux:


```
C:\Users\USER\AppData\Roaming\QGIS\QGIS3\profiles\default\python\Plugins\ORStools
```
 - Windows:


```
C:\Users\USER\AppData\Roaming\QGIS\QGIS3\profiles\default\python\Plugins\ORStools
```
 - Mac OS:


```
Library/Application Support/QGIS/QGIS3/profiles/default/python/Plugins/ORStools
```

If not found, the QGIS’ Active User Profile Folder can be accessed through “QGIS” ► “Settings” ► “User Profile” ► “Open Active Profile Folder”

C.2 Usage

- Before using a Plugin, using the Reload Plugin through “Plugin Reloader” is recommended.
- Follow the instructions detailed in Appendices C.3 to C.5 for each Plugin.

C.3 Hazards Combination

A resilience analysis should consider all potential hazards that might affect the system. Different institutions and organizations provide geolocated information about simple hazards. The user should store all simple hazards in a **QgsTreeLayer** called *Hazards*, otherwise the Python-based QGIS Plugin will not consider them. The Layers included in the **QgsTreeLayer** should contain at least the following information in its Attribute Table:

1. Field *SUMMER* → summer hazard index.
2. Field *WINTER* → winter hazard index.
3. Field *AUTUMN* → autumn hazard index.
4. Field *SPRING* → spring hazard index.

Simple hazards can simultaneously occur, increasing the vulnerabilities of the system. In that context, the Hazard Combination Plugin results in a new layer that includes the probability of having the combined events in each season of the year.

Figure 92 shows the Dialog Box of this Python-based QGIS Plugin. First, the user should select the type of combination between events: dependent or independent. Second, the user should choose *Event A* and *Event B* among all layers included in the **QgsTreeLayer** called *Hazards*.

The Python-based QGIS Plugin will unlock the $P(A|B)$ boxes when the user chooses dependent events. The user should introduce how the hazard index of *Event A* varies once *Event B* occurs. Introduce this variation using per unit (p.u.) notation: 1 signifies no variation, 0.5 represents half hazard index, and 2 indicates double hazard index.

Figure 92: Dialog Box of CITCEA Probability Analysis Python-based QGIS Plugin

The Python-based QGIS Plugin adds a new layer to the hazard database, including the combined hazard index. The new layer is generated as a temporary layer. It should be saved in the project’s folder to make it permanent. Afterwards, the layer should be moved to the QgsTreeLayer *Hazards*. Once included, the user can select the layer in subsequent event combinations.

C.4 Impact Evaluation

The Python-based QGIS Plugin, which determines each element's impact, allows the user to determine the amount of energy not supplied when a component, i.e., bus or power line, fails. The impact is determined by comparing the active power supplied when all elements are connected with the active power supplied when the analyzed element fails. The OPF objective function maximizes the active power delivered to loads.

The Python-based QGIS Plugin provides various kinds of analysis. The user can select the year's seasons in which the analysis is desired, the type of OPF, DC or AC, and a daily or instantaneous analysis. The daily analysis considers a 24-hour profile while the instantaneous analysis considers the average power, i.e., the OPF is performed for a single period.

As a result, the Python-based QGIS Plugin generates two new layers, one for buses and one for power lines. Each layer includes information about each element's impact. A .csv file is also created in the folder specified by the user. The .csv includes each element's impact and the total active power supplied by the system when all elements are connected.

A QgsTreeLayer called *System_TBA* should include the layers of the network. At least two layers are requested: one for buses and one for power lines. The Layers included in the QgsTreeLayer should contain at least the following information in the Attribute Table:

1. Buses Layer:
 - (a) Field *Name* → bus name
 - (b) Field *Voltage_kV* → voltage level
 - (c) Field *GRID* → 1 in case of being the 0 connected to the external grid, 0 otherwise.
 - (d) Field *Type_GEN* → the generators can be modeled as a PQ or PV. A PQ generator provides constant active and reactive power while a PV provides constant active power while fixing the voltage in a given setpoint.
 - (e) Field *PL_Av_Au* → average active power demanded in autumn to the bus in kW.
 - (f) Field *PL_Av_Wi* → average active power demanded in winter to the bus in kW.
 - (g) Field *PL_Av_Sp* → average active power demanded in spring to the bus in kW.
 - (h) Field *PL_Av_Su* → average active power demanded in summer to the bus in kW.
 - (i) Field *QL_Av_Au* → average reactive power demanded in autumn to the bus in kW.
 - (j) Field *QL_Av_Wi* → average reactive power demanded in winter to the bus in kW.
 - (k) Field *QL_Av_Sp* → average reactive power demanded in spring to the bus in kW.
 - (l) Field *QL_Av_Su* → average reactive power demanded in summer to the bus in kW.
 - (m) Field $\{PL_{00_Au}, \dots, QL_{24_Au}\}^*$ → average active power demanded during the corresponding hour in autumn to the bus in kW (24 fields).

- (n) Field $\{PL_{00_Wi}, \dots, QL_{24_Wi}\}^*$ → average active power demanded during the corresponding hour in winter to the bus in kW (24 fields).
- (o) Field $\{PL_{00_Sp}, \dots, QL_{24_Sp}\}^*$ → average active power demanded during the corresponding hour in spring to the bus in kW (24 fields).
- (p) Field $\{PL_{00_Su}, \dots, QL_{24_Su}\}^*$ → average active power demanded during the corresponding hour in summer to the bus in kW (24 fields).
- (q) Field $\{QL_{00_Au}, \dots, QL_{24_Au}\}^*$ → average reactive power demanded during the corresponding hour in autumn to the bus in kW (24 fields).
- (r) Field $\{QL_{00_Wi}, \dots, QL_{24_Wi}\}^*$ → average reactive power demanded during the corresponding hour in winter to the bus in kW (24 fields).
- (s) Field $\{QL_{00_Sp}, \dots, QL_{24_Sp}\}^*$ → average reactive power demanded during the corresponding hour in spring to the bus in kW (24 fields).
- (t) Field $\{QL_{00_Su}, \dots, QL_{24_Su}\}^*$ → average reactive power demanded during the corresponding hour in summer to the bus in kW (24 fields).

2. Power Lines Layer:

- (a) Field *Line_Name* → line name
- (b) Field *r_ohm_km* → resistance of the line in Ohm per km
- (c) Field *x_ohm_km* → inductance of the line in Ohm per km
- (d) Field *c_nf_km* → capacitance of the line in nano Fard
- (e) Field *i_max_kA* → maximal thermal current in kA
- (f) Field *PARALLEL* → number of parallel line systems

The *From* and *To* buses, as well as the *Length*, are automatically determined through the geolocated data.

1. * parameters only required in the hourly OPF. They can be omitted in instantaneous OPF.
2. additional fields might included though they are not going to be used in the OPF calculation.

The Dialog Box of the Plugin is represented as Figure 93.

Figure 93: Dialog Box of CITCEA Probability Analysis Python-based QGIS Plugin

First, the user should select the layers with buses and power lines in the first and second dropdown lists, respectively. The list shows all layers included in the QgsTreeLayer *System_TBA*. Second, the user should choose the year's season for the element's impact evaluation. Third, the user can select between a DC and AC OPF depending on the system characteristics, data available, and expected accuracy. Fourth, the user should choose between instantaneous or hourly OPF. Finally, the user should name a .csv file to save the element's impact obtained.

As a result, the Plugin generates two new layers, one for buses and one for power lines. The layers contain the same data in the Attribute Table as the input layers and a new Field called *Impact*. The Field *Impact* includes the amount of energy or power that would be unsupplied in case of losing the element. *Impact* is quantified in terms of power if the user selects an instantaneous analysis. Additionally, the .csv includes a list of elements and their impact. New layers are generated as temporary layers. They should be saved in the project's folder to make them permanent.

C.5 Risk Assessment and Resilience Index

A resilience analysis should consider all hazards affecting a system and its vulnerabilities. The Resilience Analysis Python-based QGIS Plugin enables risk assessment and the calculation of the system's resilience index. Figure 94 shows the Python-based QGIS Plugin Dialog Box.

Figure 94: Dialog Box of CITCEA Resilience Index Python-based QGIS Plugin

First, the user should select the year's season to analyze. Second, the user should choose the layer with buses and power lines in the dropdown lists. The dropdown lists include all layers saved in the `QgsTreeLayer System_TBA`. Third, the user can specify the maximum length of each segment of the power lines. In case of not expecting a segmentation in power lines, introduce a value a high value. Fourth, the user should introduce a .csv file with the vulnerabilities of the buses and power lines, respectively. Fifth, the user should manually introduce the sum of total impacts. Finally, the user should specify the .csv file to save the risk assessment results.

Regarding the .csv of the vulnerabilities, the minimum content should be:

1. Column name: *Name* → The name of each bus / power line. The elements should have the same name used in the layers included in `QgsTreeLayer System_TBA`. The name of each element should be repeated for each vulnerability, i.e. if an element has 10 vulnerabilities, the .csv should include 10 rows and each row should include the element's name.
2. Column name: *VULNERABILITY* → vulnerability's name. The user should specify each vulnerability in a different row.

3. Column name: *hazard-name_likelihood* → As many columns as hazards included in the QgsTree-Layer *Hazards* need to be included replacing *hazard-name* by the layer's name. In each row, the user should specify the likelihood of the vulnerability affecting the system once the hazard occurs.
4. Column name: *hazard-name_damage* → As many columns as hazards included in the QgsTreeLayer *Hazards* need to be included replacing *hazard-name* by the layer's name. In each row, the user should specify the impact that the element has on the system. Those impacts can be estimated through the Plugin detailed in Appendix C.4.

This Python-based QGIS Plugin adds two more layers to the QGIS project for buses and power lines. The Attribute Table of each layer includes the name of the element and the total power or energy risked in it. In the case of power lines, each segment is an independent feature in the resulting layer.

New layers are generated as temporary layers. They should be saved in the project's folder to make them permanent.

Finally, the .csv file includes more detailed information. The user can check the amount of power or energy risked in each element because of each vulnerability. This information might be helpful to assess the introduction of mitigation action in the system.

Annex: Multiport converter sizing use cases

D.1 Building case studies sensitivity results

This section presents the sensitivity analysis results of the building case studies. The following figures show the storage capacity and 1/C-rate of the BESS, as well as the nominal power of the multiport converter terminals. The parameters of Table 7 are considered, but only those cases where the BESS appears are plotted. Results show that ICAT headquarters and Castelló d’Empúries health center have similar performance. But in Garrotxa Regional Hospital, the BESS is not economically feasible unless it has a cost lower than 150 €/kWh and the grid price increases significantly.

D.1.1 ICAT headquarters

Figure 95: Nominal power of the MPC terminal connected to the PV of ICAT headquarters considering sensitivity parameters of Table 7

Figure 96: Nominal power of the MPC terminal connected to the external grid and loads of ICAT headquarters considering sensitivity parameters of Table 7

Figure 97: Nominal power of the MPC terminal connected to the BESS of ICAT headquarters considering sensitivity parameters of Table 7

Figure 98: 1/C-rate of the BESS of ICAT headquarters considering sensitivity parameters of Table 7

D.1.2 Castelló d’Empúries health center

Figure 99: BESS storage capacity of Castelló d’Empúries health center considering sensitivity parameters of Table 7

Figure 100: Nominal power of the MPC terminal connected to the PV of Castelló d’Empúries health center considering sensitivity parameters of Table 7

Figure 101: Nominal power of the MPC terminal connected to the external grid and loads of Castelló d’Empúries health center considering sensitivity parameters of Table 7

Figure 102: Nominal power of the MPC terminal connected to the BESS of Castelló d’Empúries health center considering sensitivity parameters of Table 7

Figure 103: 1/C-rate of the BESS of Castelló d'Empúries health center considering sensitivity parameters of Table 7

D.1.3 Garrotxa Regional Hospital

Figure 104: BESS storage capacity of Garrotxa Regional Hospital considering sensitivity parameters of Table 7

Figure 105: Nominal power of the MPC terminal connected to the PV of Garrotxa Regional Hospital considering sensitivity parameters of Table 7

Figure 106: Nominal power of the MPC terminal connected to the external grid and loads of Garrotxa Regional Hospital considering sensitivity parameters of Table 7

Figure 107: Nominal power of the MPC terminal connected to the BESS of Garrotxa Regional Hospital considering sensitivity parameters of Table 7

Figure 108: 1/C-rate of the BESS of Garrotxa Regional Hospital considering sensitivity parameters of Table 7

D.2 LV case study results

This section presents the detailed results of the LV case study, including the plots of active and reactive power imported, line currents, bus voltages, and active and reactive power exchange of the MPC.

D.2.1 Two-terminal MPC

Figure 109: Active and reactive power import from the external grid for LV case study in the two-terminal MPC scenario

Figure 110: Line currents for LV case study in the two-terminal MPC scenario

Figure 111: Bus voltages for LV case study in the two-terminal MPC scenario

D.2.2 Extreme PV

Figure 112: Active and reactive power import from the external grid for LV case study in the extreme PV scenario

Figure 113: Line currents for LV case study in the extreme PV scenario

Figure 114: Bus voltages for LV case study in the extreme PV scenario

D.2.3 Extreme EV

Figure 115: Active and reactive power import from the external grid for LV case study in the extreme EV scenario

Figure 116: Line currents for LV case study in the extreme EV scenario

Figure 117: Bus voltages for LV case study in the extreme EV scenario

Figure 118: Active and reactive power of the MPC terminals for LV case study in the extreme EV scenario

D.3 MV case study results

D.3.1 Analysis of the general concept

Figure 119: Power factor of the MPC according to the voltage of the buses before their interconnection, for different weights on the objective function, for the simple MV case study in the first scenario

Figure 120: Power factor of the MPC according to the voltage of the buses before their interconnection, for different weights on the objective function, for the simple MV case study in the second scenario

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